

A
PROJECT REPORT
ON

**"JPEG IMPLEMENTATION USING
FPGA"**

*In Partial Fulfillment for the Requirement of the Degree of
Bachelor's in Electronics & Telecommunication
Engineering*

SUBMITTED BY

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*EXAM NO. – B3113028
EXAM NO. – B3113019*

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YEAR : 2007-2008**

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..... Man's glory lieth in his knowledge, his upright conduct, his praiseworthy character, his wisdom, and not his nationality or rank.

- Baha 'u' llah

Dedicated to All my teachers who have shaped me, some or the other way so as to sail and survive in the endless ocean of knowledge.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This report is the result of the dedication and encouragement of many individuals. Our sincere and heartfelt appreciation goes to all of them.

We are greatly indebted to our guide, Prof. A. H. Ansari, Prof. S.G. Galande, H.O.D of E&Tc department, our co-guide Prof. A. M. Kolhe for their guidance, encouragement and critical review of the project work.

In particular, we wish to acknowledge the numerous efforts taken Mr. Chakradhar Borkute, C.E.O. of Qualitat Systems, our external guide Mr. Amit Gangwar, Design Engineer (VLSI), Mr. Swapnil sir and Miss. Chetana madam for their guidance and assistance which eventually led to the success of the project work.

Grateful appreciation is offered to the following individuals for their contribution in our project work. Prof. P.G. Vispute, Prof. S.A. Shaikh, Prof. M.S. Tadpatrikar, Prof. T. A. More and other teaching and non teaching staff members of the department.

We are indebted to a number of individuals in academic circle as well as in industry who have contributed to this project work. Their contributions have been important in so many different ways that we find it difficult to acknowledge them but we wish to acknowledge all of them for their favors towards us.

At last, as a personal note we are grateful to our family members and friends for the encouragement and invaluable support which has been the backbone of our determination while working on the project.

Declaration: The work presented in the report titled “JPEG implementation using FPGA” is a result of investigation carried out by the following students.

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PREFACE

If computer science is fundamentally the study of information, the first question that arises is, what is information? Unfortunately although the concept of information is the bedrock of the entire field, the question can not be answered precisely. In this sense the concept of information in computer science is similar to the concepts of point, line and plane in geometry they are all undefined terms about which statements can be made but which can not be explained in terms of more elementary concepts.

The introduction of computers in the field of Digital Image Processing (DIP) due to the advancement in complex and faster computing capability has led to an entirely new phase of DIP. Interest in DIP methods stems from two application areas “improvement of pictorial information for human interpretation and processing of image data for storage, transmission and representation for autonomous machine perception”. This report has several objectives 1). To define the scope of the field that we call image processing. 2). To give an idea of the state of art in image processing using VLSI technique. 3). To discuss briefly the implementation of DCT algorithm using vector processing method. 4). To give an overview of the components/modules used in JPEG system implementation on an FPGA chip. In this report the first Chapter gives an insight to the basics of image compression consisting of the fundamental issues and concepts of image compression. The second chapter gives a brief description of the baseline JPEG codec and elaborates the functions included in that. The third chapter is the most significant part of the report which focuses on the actual implementation of DCT, implementation strategy, testing methodology and design steps for working with an Xilinx FPGA. The fourth chapter briefs about the results obtained through Matlab and VHDL and comparison between them is shown also short discussion along with the future work that can be done to get the optimized solution. The fifth chapter concludes the report fulfilling the objectives of the JPEG algorithm. The sixth chapter consists of the system overview in detail. Finally the seventh chapter gives a list of some of the cited references used for the project work. All the issues mentioned have been elaborated in a brief and précised manner.

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ABSTRACT

Image compression is an important topic in commercial, industrial, and academic applications. Whether it is in commercial photography, industrial imaging, or video, digital pixel information can comprise considerably large amounts of data. Management of such data can involve significant overhead in computational complexity, storage, and data processing. Typical access speeds for storage mediums are inversely proportional to capacity. Through data compression, such tasks can be optimized. Image and video compressors and decompressors (codecs) are implemented mainly in software as digital signal processors have optimized instruction sets to manage the required operations. Hardware-specific codecs can be integrated into digital systems fairly easily, requiring work only in the areas of interface and overall integration. Improvements in speed occur primarily because the hardware can be tailored to the compression algorithm as well as the application. Using an FPGA to implement a codec combines the better of two worlds: significantly increased processing speed due to the use of customized hardware, and flexibility to make changes and tunings of the algorithm since FPGA-based designs are easily modified.

The DCT, the one we are implementing here is lossy compression technique. An image reconstructed following lossy compression contains degradation relative to the original. Often this is because the compression scheme completely discards redundant information. However, lossy schemes are capable of achieving much higher compression. Under normal viewing conditions, no visible loss is perceived (visually lossless). One-dimensional DCT has most often been used in two dimensional DCT, by employing the row-column decomposition, which is also more suitable for hardware implementation. Typically the DCT coefficients produced have most of the block's energy in a few frequency domain elements, and hence quantization and coding is applied after DCT to provide the actual compression. This core can perform the two dimensional Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT) on an 8x8 block of samples. The simple, fully synchronous design allows for fast operation while maintaining a low gate count. It offers high performance and many features to meet your multimedia, digital video and digital printing applications.

CHAPTER 1

Introduction

1.1 IMAGE COMPRESSION

Image compression is an important topic in the digital world. Whether it is commercial photography, industrial imagery, or video. A digital image bitmap can contain considerably large amounts of data causing exceptional overhead in both computational complexity as well as data processing. Storage media has exceptional capacity; however, access speeds are typically inversely proportional to capacity. [8] Compression is important to manage large amounts of data for network, internet, or storage media. Compression techniques have been studied for years, and will continue to improve. Typically image and video compressors and decompressors (CODECS) are performed mainly in software as signal processors can manage these operations without incurring too much overhead in computation. However, the complexity of these operations can be efficiently implemented in hardware. Hardware specific CODECS can be integrated into digital systems fairly easily. Improvements in speed occur primarily because the hardware is tailored to the compression algorithm rather than to handle a broad range of operations like a digital signal processor. Data compression itself is the process of reducing the amount of information into a smaller data set that can be used to represent, and reproduce the information. Types of image compression include lossless compression, and lossy compression techniques that are used to meet the needs of Specific applications.

JPEG compression can be used as a lossless or a lossy process depending on the requirements of the application. Both lossless and lossy compression techniques employ reduction of redundant data. Work in standardization has been controlled by the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) in cooperation with the International Electro technical Commission (IEC). The Joint Photographic Experts Group produced the well-known image format JPEG, a widely used image format. [2] JPEG provides a solid baseline compression algorithm that can be modified numerous ways to fit any desired application. The JPEG specification was released initially in 1991, although it does not specify a particular implementation.

1.2 REDUNDANCY CODING

To compress data, it is important to recognize redundancies in data, in the form of coding redundancy, inter-pixel redundancy, and psycho-visual redundancy. [3] Data redundancies occur when unnecessary data is used to represent source information. Compression is achieved when one or more of these types of redundancies are reduced. [3] Intuitively, removing unnecessary data will decrease the size of the data, without losing any important information. However, this is not the case for psycho-visual redundancy. The most obvious way to reduce compression is to reduce the coding redundancy. This is referring to the entropy of an image in the sense that more data is used than necessary to convey the information. Lossless redundancy removal compression techniques are classified as entropy coding. Other compression can be obtained through inter-pixel redundancy removal. Each adjacent pixel is highly related to its neighbors, thus can be differentially encoded rather than sending the entire value of the pixel. Similarly adjacent blocks have the same property, although not too the extent of pixels. In order to produce error free compression, it is recommended that only coding redundancy is reduced or eliminated. [3] This means that the source image will be exactly the same as the decompressed image. However, inter-pixel redundancies can also be removed, as the exact pixel value can be reconstructed from differential coding or through run length coding. Psycho-visual redundancy refers to the fact that the human visual system will interpret an image in a way such that removal of this redundancy will create an image that is nearly indistinguishable by human viewers. The main way to reduce this redundancy is through quantization. Quantizing data will reduce it to levels Defined by the quantization value. Psycho-visual properties are taken advantage of from studies performed on the human visual system.

1.3 THE HUMAN VISUAL SYSTEM

The Human Visual System (HVS) describes the way that the human eye processes an image, and relays it to the brain. By taking advantage of some properties of HVS, a lot of compression can be achieved. In general, the human eye is more sensitive to low frequency components, and the overall brightness or luminance of the image. Images contain both low frequency and high frequency components. Low frequencies correspond to slowly varying color, whereas high frequencies represent fine detail

within the image. Intuitively, low frequencies are more important to create a good representation of an image. Higher frequencies can largely be ignored to a certain degree. The human eye is more sensitive to the luminance (brightness), than the chrominance (color difference) of an image. Thus during compression, chrominance values are less important and quantization can be used to reduce the amount of psycho-visual redundancy. Luminance data can be quantized, but more coarsely to ensure that important data is not lost. Several compression algorithms use transforms to change the image from pixel values representing color to frequencies dealing with light and dark of an image, not frequencies of light. Many forms of the JPEG compressions algorithm make use of the discrete cosine transform. Other transforms such as wavelets are employed by other compression algorithms. These models take advantage of subjective redundancy by exploiting the human visual system sensitivity to image characteristics. [1]

1.4 TRANSFORM CODING

Another form of compression technique aside from exploiting redundancies in data is known as transform coding or block quantization. Transform coding employs techniques such as Differential pulse code modulation as well as other predictive compression measures. Transform coding works by moving data from spatial components to transform space such that data is reduced into a fewer number of samples. Transform coders effectively create an output that has a majority of the energy compacted into a smaller number of transform coefficients. [8]The JPEG image compression algorithm makes use of a discrete cosine transform to move pixel data representing color intensities to frequency domain. Most multimedia systems combine both transform coding and entropy coding into a hybrid coding technique. [5] The most efficient transform coding technique employs the Karhunen-Loeve-Hotelling (KLH) transform. The KLH transform has the best results of any studied transform regarding the best energy compaction. However, the KLH transform has no fast algorithm or effective hardware implementation. Thus, JPEG compression replaces the KLH transform with the discrete cosine transform, which is closely related to the discrete Fourier transform. Transform coders typically make use of quantizers to scale the transform coefficients to achieve greater compression. As a majority of energy from the source image is compacted into few coefficients, vector quantizers can be used to coarsely quantize the components with little to no useful

information, and finely quantize the more important coefficients. A major benefit to transform coding is that distortion or noise produced by quantization and rounding gets evenly distributed over the resulting image through the inverse transform. [8]

1.5 LOSSLESS COMPRESSION

Lossless compression techniques work by removing redundant information as well as removing or reducing information that can be recreated during decompression. [2] Lossless compression is ideal, as source data will be recreated without error. However, this leads to small compression ratios and will most likely not meet the needs of many applications. Compression ratios are highly dependent on input data, thus lossless compression will not meet the requirements of applications requiring a constant data rate or data size. Lossless techniques employ entropy encoders such as Huffman encoders. Huffman produced an efficient variable length coding scheme in 1952. [2] Such encoders similar to PKZIP, a popular public domain compression program, make use of order and patterning within data sets. This property allows entropy coding, such as run length coding, to compress data without any loss. Entropy encoders give a codeword to each piece of data. The codeword is of variable length to enhance compression. The varying length is typically determined by the frequency that a certain piece of data appears. Some algorithms generate codeword's after analyzing the data set, and others use standard codeword's already generated based off of average statistics. Shorter codeword's are assigned to those values appearing more frequently, where longer codeword's are assigned to those values that occur less frequently. This is the property that the Morse Alphabet was created off of. Applying Morse coding to the English language, vowels such as 'e' occur most frequently, so small codeword's are assigned. Other letters such as 'z' and 'q' occur much less frequently and thus are assigned longer codeword's. These same principles are the foundation for many entropy encoders. Run length coding, another form of entropy coding, was created to exploit the nature of inter-pixel redundancy. As each pixel is highly correlated to its neighbors, it can be expected that certain values will be repeated in adjacent pixels. By encoding this data repetition as a run length, significant compression can be achieved. When employed in lossy compression systems, run length coding can achieve significant compression compared to lossless compression; especially after quantization. The best known lossless image compression algorithm is the CompuServe Graphics Interchange Format (GIF).

Unfortunately the GIF format cannot handle compression of images with resolutions greater than 8-bits per pixel. Another lossless format called the Portable Network Graphics (PNG) can compress images with 24-bit or 48-bit color resolutions.

1.6 LOSSY COMPRESSION

The main benefit of lossy compression is that the data rate can be reduced. This is necessary as certain applications require high compression ratios along with accelerated data rates. Of course significant compression can be achieved simply by removing a lot of information and hence quality from the source image, but this is often inappropriate. Lossy compression algorithms attempt to maximize the benefits of compression ratio and bit rate, while minimizing loss of quality. [2] Finding optimal ways to reach this goal is a severely complicated process as many factors must be taken into account. Variables such as a quality factor which is used to scale the quantization tables used in JPEG can either reduce the resulting image quality with higher compression ratios, or conversely improve image quality with lower compression ratios. JPEG, although lossy, can give higher compression ratios than GIF while leaving the human observer with little to complain of loss in quality. Minimizing the variance between source and compressed image formats, otherwise known as Mean Square Error, is the ultimate goal for lossy compression algorithms. Compression induced loss in images can cause both missing image features as well as artifacts added to the picture. Artifacts are caused by noise produced by sources such as quantization, and may show up as blocking within the image. Blocking artifacts within an image can become apparent with higher compression ratios. The edges are representative of blocks used during compression, such as 8x8 blocks of pixels, used in JPEG. Strangely, artifacts such as noise or ringing may actually improve the subjective quality of the image. [2] Noise can cause contouring which shows up in gradual shading regions of the image, while ringing is apparent at sharp edges. JPEG unfortunately does not do well with computer generated graphics.

1.7 COLOR SPACE

Compression also can come from the way color is represented within pixel data values. Monochrome images simply use one number to indicate the luminance of the sample. [1] In order to represent color within an image several values are used. There are several formats used to represent color, the two most common being RGB and

Luminance/Chrominance, which both employ three-value pixel representations. The RGB format represents a colored image in three separate parts. Each of the three samples represents the same image, just the relative proportions of red, green, and blue for each given pixel. [1] These are primary colors so any color or shade can be produced by a combination of red, green, and blue intensities. This is known as additive coloring. The other most commonly used format is luminance(Y), along with two chrominance components (Cr and Cb). Cr and Cb represent the chrominance, or color difference within the sample. Actually there are three components to chrominance, Cr, Cb, and Cg for red, blue, and green chrominance. However, Cg can be derived from Y, Cr, and Cb. Thus only two components need be compressed as the image translator can infer the third based upon the other two. The two chrominance values make up a two-dimensional vector, where the phase gives the hue, and the magnitude gives color saturation. Chrominance is the color quality of light Defined by its wavelength. Using luminance and chrominance has major advantages for compression in comparison to RGB. Most importantly luminance and chrominance values are separated rather than being incorporated in the same value such as RGB. RGB includes both values in each respective color. As the human visual system is less sensitive to color, the chrominance values can be further reduced in compression techniques while not severely altering the image as seen by a human observer. Luminance values alone can recreate an accurate monochrome image.

1.8 JPEG COMPRESSION

JPEG compression is defined as a lossy coding system which is based on the discrete cosine transform. However, there are several extensions to the JPEG algorithm to provide greater compression, higher precision, and can be tailored to specific applications. [3] It can also be used as a lossless coding system that may be necessary for applications requiring precise image restoration. JPEG has four defined extension modes: sequential DCT based, progressive DCT based, lossless, and hierarchical mode.

1.8.1 Sequential DCT Based

The sequential DCT based mode of operation comprises the baseline JPEG algorithm. This technique can produce very good compression ratios, while sacrificing image quality. The sequential DCT based mode achieves much of its compression through

quantization, which removes entropy from the data set. Although this baseline algorithm is transform based, it does use some measure of predictive coding called the differential pulse code modulation (DPCM). After each input 8x8 block of pixels is transformed to frequency space using the DCT, the resulting block contains a single DC component, and 63 AC components. The DC component is predicatively encoded through a difference between the current DC value and the previous. This mode only uses Huffman coding models, not arithmetic coding models which are used in JPEG extensions. This mode is the most basic, but still has a wide acceptance for its high compression ratios, which can fit many general applications very well.

1.8.2 Progressive DCT Based

Progressive DCT based JPEG compression actually uses two complimentary coding methods. [9] The goal of this extension is to display low quality images during compression which successively improve. The first method for such a technique is known as spectral-selection. This implies that data is compressed in bands. The first band contains DC components and a very few AC components to get an image that is somewhat discernable. The second method employed is known as successive approximation. This method at first will grossly quantize the coefficients after the DCT, which will result in a small data set, which will incur large amounts of blocky artifacts during decompression. The following scans will contain information about the difference between the quantized and non-quantized coefficients, using finer quantization steps. This will allow the image to slowly come into focus during decompression. Again, this method is used in applications where these features are desired.

1.8.3 Lossless Mode

Quite simply, this mode of JPEG experiences no loss when comparing the source image, to the reproduced image. This method does not use the discrete cosine transform, rather it uses predictive, differential coding. As it is lossless, it also rules out the use of quantization. This method does not achieve high compression ratios, but some applications do require extremely precise image reproduction.

1.8.4 Hierarchical Mode

The hierarchical JPEG extension uses a multi-stage compression approach, with prediction, and can use the encoding methods from the progressive, sequential or lossless modes of operation. The strategy is to down sample the image in each dimension. Then code this data set using one of the three methods discussed, lossless, sequential, or progressive. The resulting encoded data stream is to be decoded, and up-sampled to recreate the source image. Then the process encodes the difference between the recreated image and the source. This process can be repeated multiple times.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

In computing, JPEG is a commonly used method of compression for photographic images. The name JPEG stands for Joint Photographic Experts Group, the name of the committee that created the standard. The group was organized in 1986, issuing a standard in 1992 which was approved in 1994 as ISO 10918-1. JPEG is distinct from MPEG (Moving Picture Experts Group) which produces compression schemes for video. The JPEG standard specifies both the codec, which defines how an image is compressed into a stream of bytes and decompressed back into an image, and the file format used to contain that stream. The compression method is usually lossy compression, meaning that some visual quality is lost in the process, although there are variations on the standard baseline JPEG which are lossless. There is also an interlaced "Progressive JPEG" format, in which data is compressed in multiple passes of progressively higher detail. This is ideal for large images that will be displayed whilst downloading over a slow connection, allowing a reasonable preview before all the data has been retrieved. However, progressive JPEGs are not as widely supported. The file format is known as 'JPEG Interchange Format', as specified in Annex B of the standard. This is often confused with the JPEG File Interchange Format (JFIF), a minimal version of the JPEG format that was deliberately simplified so that it could be widely implemented and thus become the de-facto standard. Most image editing software programs that write to a "JPEG file" are actually creating a file in JFIF format.[1]

Image files that employ JPEG compression are commonly called "JPEG files". The most common file extension for this format is .jpg, though .jpeg, .jpe, .jfif and .jif are also used. It is also possible for JPEG data to be embedded in other file types, such as TIFF format images. JPEG/JFIF is the format most used for storing and transmitting photographs on the World Wide Web. For this application, it is preferred to formats such as GIF, which has a limit of 256 distinct colors that is insufficient for color photographs, and PNG, which produces much larger image files for this type of image. The JPEG compression algorithm is not as well suited for line drawings and other textual or iconic graphics, and thus the PNG and GIF formats are preferred for these types of images.

2.1 JOINT PHOTOGRAPHIC EXPERTS GROUP

JPEG uses a lossy compression which means that image quality is lost in the process of compressing the image. JPEG compression works by first converting the image from RGB to YUV which stores information about each pixel using brightness, hue and saturation. Then it reduces the amount of information it stores for hue and saturation since differences are less noticeable to the human eye. In trying to decrease the file size of the JPEG (for example, when using the quality slider in Photoshop), you'll tend to notice artefacts occur in flat colour areas and especially near edges. As a result, JPEG is best used for images that have more of a variation in colours. For example, images with gradients or photographs can handle a lower quality setting with little noticeable loss in quality. Images with text or large solid backgrounds are best left for GIF.

File compression methods for most other file formats are lossless and lossless means "fully recoverable". Lossless compression always returns the original data, bit-for-bit identical without any question about differences (losses). We are used to saving data to a file, and getting it all back when we next open that file. Our Word and Excel documents, our Quicken data, any data at all, we cannot imagine NOT getting back exactly the original data. TIF, PNG, GIF, BMP and most other image file formats are lossless too. This integrity requirement does limit efficiency, limiting compression of photo image data to maybe only 10% to 40% reduction in practice (graphics can be smaller). But most compression methods have full lossless recoverability as the first requirement.

JPG files don't work that way. JPG is a big exception. JPG compression is not lossless. JPG compression is lossy. Lossy means "with losses" to image quality. JPG compression has very high efficiency (relatively tiny files) because it is intentionally designed to be lossy, designed to give very small files without the requirement for full recoverability. JPG modifies the image pixel data (color values) to be more convenient for its compression method. Tiny detail that doesn't compress well (minor color changes) can be ignored (not retained). This allows amazing size reductions on the remainder, but when we open the file and expand the data to access it again, it is no longer the same data as before. This lost data is like lost purity or integrity. It can vary in degree, it can be fairly good, but it is always unrecoverable corruption of the data. This makes JPG be quite different from all the other usual file format choices.

This will sound preachy, but if your use is critical, you need a really good reason to use JPG.

There are times and places this compromise is an advantage. Web pages and email files need to be very small, to be fast through the modem, and some uses may not need maximum quality. In some cases, we are willing to compromise quality for size, sacrificing for the better good. And this is the purpose of JPG. There is no magic answer providing both high compression and high quality. We don't get something for nothing, and the small size has a cost in quality. Still, mild quality losses may sometimes be acceptable for less critical purposes. The sample JPG images on next page show the kind of problem to expect from excessive compression.

Even worse, more quality is lost every time the JPG file is compressed and saved again, so ever editing and saving a JPG image again is a questionable decision. You should instead just discard the old JPG file and start over from your archived lossless TIF master, saving that change as the new JPG copy you need. JPG compression can be selected to be better quality in a larger file, or to be lesser quality in a smaller file. When you save a JPG file, your FILE - SAVE AS dialog box should have an option for the degree of file compression.

Many programs (Photoshop, Elements, Photo Impact, Photo Deluxe) call this setting JPG Quality. Other programs (Paint Shop Pro and Corel) call it JPG Compression, which is the same thing, except Quality runs numerically the opposite direction from Compression. High Quality corresponds to Low Compression. Typical values might be 85 Quality, or 15 Compression. These numbers are relative and have no absolute meaning. Compression in one program will vary from another even at the same number. The number is also not a percentage of anything, and Quality 100 does NOT mean any compression, it is just an arbitrary starting point. JPG will always compress, and Quality 90 is not so different from Quality 100 in practice. There's very little improvement over 95.

2.2 JPEG: DCT-BASED IMAGE CODING STANDARD

The idea of compressing an image is not new. The discovery of DCT in 1974 [1] is an important achievement for the research community working on image compression. The DCT can be regarded as a discrete-time version of the Fourier-Cosine series. It is a close relative of DFT, a technique for converting a signal into elementary frequency components. Thus DCT can be computed with a Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) like algorithm in $O(n \log n)$ operations. Unlike DFT, DCT is real-valued and provides a better approximation of a signal with fewer coefficients. The DCT of a discrete signal $x(n)$, $n=0, 1, \dots, N-1$ is defined as:

$$X(u) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{N}} C(u) \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} x(n) \cos\left(\frac{(2N+1)un}{2N}\right)$$

Where, $C(u) = 0.707$ for $u = 0$ and 1 otherwise.

In 1992, JPEG established the first international standard for still image compression where the encoders and decoders are DCT-based. The JPEG standard specifies three modes namely sequential, progressive, and hierarchical for lossy encoding, and one mode of lossless encoding. The baseline JPEG coder which is the sequential encoding in its simplest form, will be briefly discussed here. Fig. 12(a) and 12(b) show the key processing steps in such an encoder and decoder for grayscale images. Color image compression can be approximately regarded as compression of multiple grayscale images, which are either compressed entirely one at a time, or are compressed by alternately interleaving 8x8 sample blocks from each in turn. In this article, we focus on grayscale images only.

2.3 BASELINE JPEG COMPRESSION

Fig 2.3.1: JPEG Encoder

Fig 2.3.2: JPEG Decoder

The baseline JPEG compression algorithm is the most basic form of sequential DCT based compression. By using transform coding, quantization, and entropy coding, at an 8-bit pixel resolution, a high-level of compression can be achieved. However, the compression ratio achieved is due to sacrifices made in quality. The baseline specification assumes that 8-bit pixels are the source image, but extensions can use higher pixel resolutions. JPEG assumes that each block of data input is 8x8 pixels, which are serially input in raster order. Similarly, each block is sequentially input in raster order. Baseline JPEG compression has some configurable portions, such as quantization tables, and Huffman tables, which can individually be specified in the JPEG file header. By studying the source images to be compressed, Huffman codes and quantization codes can be optimized to reach a higher level of compression without losing more quality than is acceptable. Although this mode of JPEG is not highly configurable, it still allows a considerable amount of compression. Furthermore compression can be achieved by sub sampling chrominance portions of the input image, which is a useful technique playing on the human visual system.

2.4 LEVEL SHIFT

In order to make the data fit the discrete cosine transform, each pixel value is level shifted by subtracting 128 from its value. The result of this is 8-bit pixels that have the range of -127 to 128, making the data symmetric across 0. This is good for DCT as any symmetry that is exposed will lead toward better entropy compression. Effectively this shifts the DC coefficient to fall more in line with value of the AC coefficients. The AC coefficients produced by the DCT are not affected in any way by this level shifting.

2.5 DISCRETE COSINE TRANSFORM

The discrete cosine transform is the basis for the JPEG compression standard. Ahmed, Natarajan, and Rao originally proposed use of the DCT in 1974, and it has become the most popular transform for image and video coding.[1] Many compression techniques take advantage of transform coding as it decorrelates adjacent pixels from the source image. For JPEG, this allows for efficient compression by allowing quantization on elements that are less sensitive. The DCT algorithm is completely reversible making this useful for both lossless and lossy compression techniques. The DCT is a special case of the well known Fourier transform. Essentially the Fourier transform in theory can represent a given input signal with a series of sine and cosine terms. The discrete cosine transform is a special case of the Fourier transform in which the sine components are eliminated.[4] For JPEG, a two-dimensional DCT algorithm is used, which is essentially the one-dimensional version evaluated twice. By this property there are numerous ways to efficiently implement a software or hardware based DCT module.[1] The DCT is operated two dimensionally taking into account an 8 by 8 block of pixels. The resulting data set is an 8 by 8 block of frequency space components, the Coefficients scaling the series cosine terms, known as basis functions. The first element at row 0 and column 0, is known as the DC term, the average frequency value of the entire block. The other 63 terms are AC components which represent the spatial frequencies that compose the input pixel block, by scaling the cosine terms within the series. There are two useful products of the DCT algorithm. First it has the ability to concentrate image energy into a small number of coefficients. Second, it minimizes the interdependencies between coefficients.[1] These two points essentially state why this form of transform is used for the standard JPEG compression technique. By compacting the energy within an image, more Coefficients are left to be quantized coarsely, impacting compression positively, but not losing quality in the resulting image after decompression. Taking away inter-pixel relations allows quantization to be non-linear, also affecting quantization positively. DCT has been effective in producing great pictures at low bit rates and is fairly easy to implement with fast hardware based algorithms.[3]

2.6 TRANSFORM CODING

Transform coding is widely used among compression algorithms. By taking images from the spatial domain to the frequency domain, it makes the data more amenable to compression.[1] Different techniques in transform coding yield different results. Some have exceptional performance at the cost of computational complexity. Others are easy to compute, but lose in the compression aspect. For instance, a well known transform is the Karhunen-Loeve-Hotelling transform.

This method gives the best performance by compacting energy efficiently into a minimal coefficient set. However, this technique is computationally inefficient especially during the reverse transform.[1] The DCT is one of many transform functions that is widely used among image compression algorithms. This particular one was chosen for its ability to decorrelate image pixels within the spatial domain, as well as being an orthogonal transform. An orthogonal transform such as the DCT has the good property that the inverse DCT can take its frequency coefficients back to the spatial domain at no loss. However, implementations can be lossy due to bit limitations, especially apparent in those algorithms in hardware. The DCT as determined by Ahmed, Natarajan, and Rao was discovered to be particularly close the KLH transform, in terms of performance.[1] The DCT does win in terms of computational complexity as there are numerous studies that have been completed in different techniques for evaluating the DCT. The discrete cosine transform is actually more efficient in reconstructing a given number of samples, as compared to a Fourier transform. By using the property of orthogonality of cosine, as opposed to sine, a signal can be periodically reconstructed based on a fewer number of samples. Any sine based transform is not orthogonal, and would have to take Fourier transforms of more numbers of samples to approximate a sequence of samples as a periodic signal. As the signal we are sampling, the given image, there is actually no real periodicity. If the image is run through a Fourier transform, the sine terms can actually incur large changes in amplitude for the signal, due to sine not being orthogonal. DCT will avoid this by not carrying this information to represent the changes. [2]Basis Functions The DCT is a one dimensional process that has 8 basis functions, which represent the frequency domain. Each basis function is the pixel pattern that results when that particular DCT coefficient is set to its maximum value and all the other coefficients are set to zero. The DCT essentially correlates the input image with each of the basis

functions. In the case of JPEG, a two-dimensional DCT is used, which correlates the image with 64 basis functions, shown in figure 2.1. At this point the transform has taken the input image and changed it into values within that scale each of the basis functions, to represent the input image. In the frequency domain, the new frequency values are highly separable, and can be quantized more efficiently without losing the spatial correlations that would be susceptible to the human visual system.

Figure 2.6.1: DCT Basis Functions

2.7 ZIGZAG SCANNING

The zigzag process is an approximate ordering of the basis functions from low to high spatial frequencies. This process will give more compression by putting more order in the entropy. Essentially our lower-frequency components, which describe the gradual luminance changes, are more important to the human visual system than the high frequency changes. By ordering the more important coefficients in the beginning of the 8x8 block, we can expect more runs of zeros later after quantization, toward the end of the 8x8 block. This will aid in further compression in the entropy encoding that will be discussed later.

2.8 QUANTIZATION

Quantization is an extremely important step in the JPEG compression algorithm, as it removes a considerable amount of information, thus reducing the entropy in the input data stream. Unfortunately, quantization is irreversible making Baseline JPEG lossy.[6] Quantization alone, is essentially a lossy compression technique. However, quantization does benefit the compression process, regardless of the lossy artifacts that are produced. The high frequency AC Coefficients typically will become zero, which aids in entropy coding. Quantization is intended to remove the less important components to the visual reproduction of the image.[1] Baseline JPEG allows for

custom quantization tables to be defined within the encoded file headers. The quantization tables can be linear or non-linear. However, quantization is most effective when less important elements are quantized more coarsely. Larger quantization values will result in visual artifacts. Non-zero AC Coefficients after quantization are worse for compression, but will suppress blocking artifacts in the reconstructed image. Blocking artifacts indicate high spatial frequencies caused by an absence of AC coefficients.[6] Essentially, quantization, when used effectively, will result in high compression, with minimal loss in quality.

2.9 TYPES OF QUANTIZERS

Quantizers can either be linear or non-linear. Linear quantization is when input values map to a set of evenly distributed output values. This is adequate when a high level of precision is required across the entire range of possible input values.[1] Non-linear modes treat each input value differently. Scale Factor The scale factor is often a main parameter to control image quality and compression in an image codec.[1] The change in the factor will adjust the number of steps in the resulting quantized value. Larger quantization steps will lead to greater distortion and a smaller resulting data set. The smaller the steps will distort less, but will create a larger resulting data set.[6] Tables essentially determine the quality of the output image. Fortunately, in the baseline JPEG algorithm, custom tables are allowed as long as they are Defined in the compressed JPEG file headers. The tables should take into account that the human visual system is less sensitive to amplitude errors at higher frequency coefficients. Thus, those should be quantized coarsely.[2] For better performance, different tables are used for quantizing luminance and chrominance data sets. This is because the human visual system is more sensitive to brightness changes, rather than color difference. The DCT process concentrates the energy of the data set into the upper left hand corner Coefficients of the 8x8 block, and the quantization matrix will emphasize this.[2]

2.10 DC DIFFERENTIAL CODING

To further add to the compression sequence, a process called Differential pulse code modulation or DC Differential coding is used to reduce the entropy of the data set. Essentially, this process allows the first DC value of the first block to be passed through to the entropy coding module. Afterward, the value passed is a difference

between the current block DC value and the previous block. This is done in raster order throughout all blocks of the image. Adjacent blocks in a given image contain a high degree of similarity in both color and luminance. This makes the DC Differential coding perform in a better way, by reducing more entropy in the data stream. After the first block, the DC terms after the difference module, will become zero or close to zero in many cases. This simple step actually adds to the compression substantially. Much like quantization, this step is used to reduce entropy in the data stream.

$$DIFF = DC_i - DC_{i-1}$$

2.11 ENTROPY CODING

Entropy is a measure of disorder and unpredictability. The degree of entropy can be used as a measure of the information carried by the message.[2] Up to this point the input image has run through the DCT process, followed by zigzag ging to approximately organize the data stream with more entropy toward the beginning of the stream. Then this stream was quantized, and run through the DC differencing in an effect to reduce entropy in the data stream. All of these processes both add to compression, and more importantly, make the data stream ready for entropy coding.

2.12 RUN LENGTH CODING

The first step in entropy coding is known as run length coding. This is a simple thought that is accomplished by assigning a code, run length and size, to every non-zero value in the quantized data stream. The run length is a count of zero values before the non-zero value occurred. The size is a category given to the non-zero value which is used to recover the value later. The DC value of the block is omitted in this process. Additionally, with every non-zero value a magnitude is generated which determines the number of bits that are necessary to reconstruct the value. It will indicate possible values in the size category that can be correct.[2] Run Length coding is a basic form of lossless compression. Essentially, this process is a generalization of zero suppression techniques. Zero suppression assumes that one symbol or value appears often in a data stream. [5] After quantization the goal is that most high frequency components, which are less important to the human visual system, are set to zero. The zigzag process organized the sequence to have the lower frequency components which are less likely to be zero in the first part of the data stream. This

effectively has organized the data to have larger runs of zeros, especially at the end, making the run length coding very efficient.

2.13 HUFFMAN CODING

Huffman coding is a technique which will assign a variable length codeword to an input data item. Huffman coding assigns a smaller codeword to an input that occurs more frequently. It is very similar to Morse code, which assigned smaller pulse combinations to letters that occurred more frequently. Huffman coding is variable length coding, where characters are not coded to a fixed number of bits.[5] This is the last step in the encoding process. It organizes the data stream into a smaller number of output data packets by assigning unique codeword's that later during decompression can be reconstructed without loss. For the JPEG process, each combination of run length and size category, from the run length coder, are assigned a Huffman codeword.

2.14 ERROR

The baseline JPEG algorithm is a lossy compression algorithm. It is expected that decompression will lead to artifacts that are introduced by factors such as error in the JPEG compression process. Starting with the discrete cosine transform, the transform is in itself a lossless process. However, when implemented if there are a finite number of bits used, such as in hardware, there will be truncation in the output data. Although this does not explain all artifacts and errors in the reproduced image, it does add to the problem. Quantization adds a majority of the error in the reconstructed image, as the process is irreversible. The DC Differential coding, and entropy coding are lossless as well. Errors in reconstructed images are mainly artifacts due to quantization. In quantization we give up more information on high frequency components, which are less important to the human visual system, but still there is a non-zero amount of information lost. Errors in images typically come in the form of blocky artifacts around high frequency components, sharp edges, high amounts of color difference, and areas of fine detail. Fortunately the baseline JPEG algorithm still holds enough of the information to make the error between the source and resulting images acceptable to the human eye.

2.15 JPEG FILE CONSTRUCTION

The JPEG header format is necessary for several reasons. The headers both Define the image type, size, quality, and more importantly it has information that the decoder must use to correctly reproduce the image. The headers are prescribed by the JPEG File Interchange Format specification, otherwise known as JFIF. The format has several header sections, each of which begins with a two-byte header, which is a unique symbol that will not be mistaken. The file structure allows for multiple scans of entropy coded segments, each which could use different Huffman tables, and such. There is a number of optional components to the header associated with JPEG files. Figure 2.2 depicts the minimum required set of headers which are used for Baseline JPEG. Markers are used to define the header segments. A marker will always begin with the first byte as 0xFF, and the second byte Defines which type of marker it is. The first byte is uniquely identified by the decoder as a header marker. To ensure that a marker is not mistakenly created in the entropy encoded bit stream, whenever a 0xFF is encountered, a byte 0 byte (0x00) is stuffed into the data stream after 0xFF. This is known as zero stuffing. The minimum required headers for Baseline JPEG Compression are shown in table 2.1.

Figure 2.15: Frame structure for baseline JPEG

Marker	Symbol	Description
0xFFD8	SOI	Start of Image Marker
0xFFE0	APP0	Application Specific Marker
0xFFDB	DQT	Define Quantization Table Marker
0xFFC0	SOF	Start of Frame Marker
0xFFC4	DHT	Define Huffman Table Marker
0xFFDA	SOS	Start of Scan Marker
0xFFD9	EOI	End of Image Marker

Table 2.1: Headers in baseline JPEG

2.15.1 Application Specific Data Header

The application Specific data header, shown in figure 2.3, is used to define that this file is compliant to the JPEG File Interchange Format, and gives some Specific image details. This header is useful as it gives a format that can allow the JPEG bit streams to be exchanged between a wide variety of platforms and applications. Additionally, a thumbnail image can be Defined and included in this header, but this is not a requirement of the Baseline JPEG specification.

Figure 2.15.1: Application Specific Header

APP0 Header - 2 Bytes

Application Specific marker APP0, 0xFFE0. This uniquely defines the application Specific header.

Length - 2 Bytes

Total Length of header including two bytes used to specify length, but does not include header APP0.

Application Identifier - 5 Bytes

Specifically identifies JFIF through ASCII hex codes, 0x4A46494600.

Version Identifier - 2 Bytes

Specifies major and minor version numbers for JFIF, currently version 1.01 (0x0101).

Density Units - 1 Byte

Specifies units used to give pixel densities in the following entries. 0 signifies density given in pixels. 1 denotes density given in dots per inch. 2 specifies density given in dots per cm.

X Density - 2 Bytes

Horizontal pixel density in units specified.

Y Density - 2 Bytes

Vertical pixel density in units specified.

X Thumbnail

If a thumbnail is defined in this header segment, this specifies the horizontal pixel count of the thumbnail.

Y Thumbnail

If a thumbnail is defined in this header segment, this specifies the vertical pixel count of the thumbnail.

RGBn - 3n Bytes

24-bit RGB values given for thumbnail. (n) is given as X thumbnail * Y thumbnail. If X or Y Thumbnail entries are 0, this section is not necessary.

CHAPTER 3

PROJECT DETAILS

The discrete cosine transform (DCT) is a technique for converting a signal into elementary frequency components. It is widely used in image compression. Here we develop some simple functions to compute the DCT and to compress images.

These functions illustrate the power of Mathematica in the prototyping of image processing algorithms.

The rapid growth of digital imaging applications, including desktop publishing, multimedia, teleconferencing, and high-definition television (HDTV) has increased the need for effective and standardized image compression techniques. Among the emerging standards are JPEG, for compression of still images [Wallace 1991]; MPEG, for compression of motion video [Puri 1992]; and CCITT H.261 (also known as Px64), for compression of video telephony and teleconferencing. All three of these standards employ a basic technique known as the discrete cosine transform (DCT). Developed by Ahmed, Natarajan, and Rao [1974], the DCT is a close relative of the discrete Fourier transform (DFT). Its application to image compression was pioneered by Chen and Pratt [1984]. In this article, I will develop some simple functions to compute the DCT and show how it is used for image compression. We have used these functions in our laboratory to explore methods of optimizing image compression for the human viewer, using information about the human visual system [Watson 1993]. The goal of this paper is to illustrate the use of Mathematica in image processing and to provide the reader with the basic tools for further exploration of this subject.

3.1 DISCRETE COSINE TRANSFORM (DCT)

- **ONE DIMENSIONAL DCT** - The one-dimensional DCT is useful in processing one-dimensional signals such as speech waveforms.
- **TWO DIMENSIONAL DCT** - For analysis of two-dimensional (2D) signals such as images, we need a 2D version of the DCT.

Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT) is a lossy compression scheme where an $N \times N$ image block is transformed from the spatial domain to the DCT domain. DCT

decomposes the signal into spatial frequency components called DCT coefficients. The lower frequency DCT coefficients appear toward the upper left-hand corner of the DCT matrix, and the higher frequency coefficients are in the lower right-hand corner of the DCT matrix. The Human Visual System (HVS) is less sensitive to errors in high frequency coefficients than it is to lower frequency coefficients. Because of this, the higher frequency components can be more finely quantized, as done by the quantization matrix. Each value in the quantization matrix is pre-scaled by multiplying by a single value, known as the quantizer scale code. This value can range in value from one to 112 and is modifiable on a macro block basis. Dividing each DCT coefficient by an integer scale factor and rounding the results accomplishes quantization. This sets the higher frequency coefficients (in the lower right corner), that are less significant to the compressed picture, to zero by quantizing in larger steps. The low frequency coefficients (in the upper left corner) are more significant to the compressed picture, are quantized in smaller steps. The goal of quantization is to force as many of the DCT coefficients to zero, or near zero, as possible within the boundaries of the prescribed bit-rate and video quality parameters. Thus, since quantization throws away some information, it is a lossy compression scheme. Quantization can be expressed as:

$$\text{Quantizedvalue}_{(i,j)} = \frac{\text{DCT}_{(i,j)}}{\text{Quantizationmatrix}_{(i,j)}}$$

The following is a sample of the Quantization matrix used for the JPEG algorithm:

$$\text{JPEG Quantization Matrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 3 & 5 & 7 & 9 & 11 & 13 & 15 & 17 \\ 5 & 7 & 9 & 11 & 13 & 15 & 17 & 19 \\ 7 & 9 & 11 & 13 & 15 & 17 & 19 & 21 \\ 9 & 11 & 13 & 15 & 17 & 19 & 21 & 23 \\ 11 & 13 & 15 & 17 & 19 & 21 & 23 & 25 \\ 13 & 15 & 17 & 19 & 21 & 23 & 25 & 27 \\ 15 & 17 & 19 & 21 & 23 & 25 & 27 & 29 \\ 17 & 19 & 21 & 23 & 25 & 27 & 29 & 31 \end{bmatrix}$$

For most image compression standards, N = 8. An 8 x 8 block size does not have significant memory requirements, and furthermore, a block size greater than 8 x 8 does not offer significantly better compression. Each picture is divided into 16 x 16 blocks called a Macro block. Each of the macro blocks is further divided into 16

samples x 16 lines. Each block on which DCT is performed is 8-samples by 8-lines called blocks. Thus, each macro block consists of four blocks. DCT is image independent and can be performed with fast algorithms. Fast algorithms are parallel and can be efficiently implemented on parallel architecture.

Examples of standards using DCT:

- Dolby AC2 & AC3: 1-D DCT (and 1-D Discrete Sine Transform)
- JPEG (still images): 2-D DCT spatial compression
- MPEG1 & MPEG2: 2-D DCT plus motion compensation
- H.261 and H.263: moving image compression for video conferencing and video telephony

Much of the processing required to encode or decode video using these standards is taken up by calculating the DCT and/or IDCT. An efficient hardware block dedicated to these functions will improve the performance of the digital video system considerably.

3.2 TECHNICAL ASPECTS OF THE COMPRESSION ALGORITHM

The 12-bit signed input pixels provide a 16-bit signed output coefficient for the DCT. A 12-bit signed input has 11 data bits. For an 8 x 8 DCT, the 11 data bits can be multiplied eight times (represented by three bits). Multiplying 11 bits by 3 bits can result in 11 + 3 or 14 bits. Added to these 14 bits are the sign bit and the fraction bit to give a total of 16 bits. The algorithm used for the calculation of the 2D DCT is based on the following equation:

$$X_{C_{pq}} = \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} X_{mn} \cdot \frac{c(p)c(q)}{4} \cdot \cos \frac{\pi(2m+1)p}{2M} \cdot \cos \frac{\pi(2n+1)q}{2N} \quad (\text{EQ 1})$$

First, the 1D DCT of the rows are calculated and then the 1D DCT of the columns are calculated. The 1D DCT coefficients for the rows and columns can be calculated by separating equation 1 into the row part and the column part.

$$C = K \cdot \cos\left(\frac{(2 \cdot \text{col number} + 1) \cdot \text{row number} \cdot \pi}{2 \cdot M}\right) \text{ (EQ 2), where}$$

$$K = \frac{\sqrt{1}}{N} \text{ for row} = 0$$

$$K = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{N} \text{ for row} \neq 0$$

$$C^t = K \cdot \cos\left(\frac{(2 \cdot \text{row number} + 1) \cdot \text{col number} \cdot \pi}{2 \cdot N}\right) \text{ (EQ 3), where}$$

$$K = \frac{\sqrt{1}}{M} \text{ for col} = 0$$

$$K = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{M} \text{ for col} \neq 0$$

and M = total # of columns, N = total # of rows.

The constant values for C and C^t calculated from equations 2 and 3 are as follows:

$$C = \begin{bmatrix} 23170 & 23170 & 23170 & 23170 & 23170 & 23170 & 23170 & 23170 \\ 32138 & 27246 & 18205 & 6393 & -6393 & -18205 & -27246 & -32138 \\ 30274 & 12540 & -12540 & -30274 & -30274 & -12540 & 12540 & 30274 \\ 27246 & -6393 & -32138 & -18205 & 18205 & 32138 & 6393 & -27246 \\ 23170 & -23170 & -23170 & 23170 & 23170 & -23170 & -23170 & 23170 \\ 18205 & -32138 & 6393 & 27246 & -27246 & -6393 & 32138 & -18205 \\ 12540 & -30274 & 30274 & -12540 & -12540 & 30274 & -30274 & 12540 \\ 6393 & -18205 & 27246 & -32138 & 32138 & -27246 & 18205 & -6393 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$C^t = \begin{bmatrix} 23170 & 32138 & 30274 & 27246 & 23170 & 18205 & 12540 & 6393 \\ 23170 & 27246 & 12540 & -6393 & -23170 & -32138 & -30274 & -18205 \\ 23170 & 18205 & -12540 & -32138 & -23170 & 6393 & 30274 & 27246 \\ 23170 & 6393 & -30274 & -18205 & 23170 & 27246 & -12540 & -32138 \\ 23170 & -6393 & -30274 & 18205 & 23170 & -27246 & -12540 & 32138 \\ 23170 & -18205 & -12540 & 32138 & -23170 & -6393 & 30274 & -27246 \\ 23170 & -27246 & 12540 & 6393 & -23170 & 32138 & -30274 & 18205 \\ 23170 & -32138 & 30274 & -27246 & 23170 & -18205 & 12540 & -6393 \end{bmatrix}$$

For the case of 8 x 8 block region, a one-dimensional 8-point DCT/IDCT followed by an internal double buffer memory, followed by another one-dimensional 8-point DCT provides the 2D DCT architecture.

Vector processing using parallel multipliers is a method used for implementation of DCT. The advantages in the vector processing method are regular structure, simple control and interconnect, and good balance between performance and complexity of implementation.

Behavioral Model

Using vector processing, the output Y of an 8×8 DCT for input X is given by

$$Y = C \cdot X \cdot C^t,$$

Where C is the cosine coefficients and C^t are the transpose coefficients. This equation can also be written as $Y = C \cdot Z$, where

$$Z = X \cdot C^t.$$

Using the cosine C and inverse cosine C^t numbers in equation 2 and 3, the intermediate value Z can be calculated as follows:

$$X = \begin{bmatrix} x_{00} & x_{01} & x_{02} & x_{03} & x_{04} & x_{05} & x_{06} & x_{07} \\ x_{10} & x_{11} & x_{12} & x_{13} & x_{14} & x_{15} & x_{16} & x_{17} \\ x_{20} & x_{21} & x_{22} & x_{23} & x_{24} & x_{25} & x_{26} & x_{27} \\ x_{30} & x_{31} & x_{32} & x_{33} & x_{34} & x_{35} & x_{36} & x_{37} \\ x_{40} & x_{41} & x_{42} & x_{43} & x_{44} & x_{45} & x_{46} & x_{47} \\ x_{50} & x_{51} & x_{52} & x_{53} & x_{54} & x_{55} & x_{56} & x_{57} \\ x_{60} & x_{61} & x_{62} & x_{63} & x_{64} & x_{65} & x_{66} & x_{67} \\ x_{70} & x_{71} & x_{72} & x_{73} & x_{74} & x_{75} & x_{76} & x_{77} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$C^t = \begin{bmatrix} 23170 & 32138 & 30274 & 27246 & 23170 & 18205 & 12540 & 6393 \\ 23170 & 27246 & 12540 & -6393 & -23170 & -32138 & -30274 & -18205 \\ 23170 & 18205 & -12540 & -32138 & -23170 & 6393 & 30274 & 27246 \\ 23170 & 6393 & -30274 & -18205 & 23170 & 27246 & -12540 & -32138 \\ 23170 & -6393 & -30274 & 18205 & 23170 & -27246 & -12540 & 32138 \\ 23170 & -18205 & -12540 & 32138 & -23170 & -6393 & 30274 & -27246 \\ 23170 & -27246 & 12540 & 6393 & -23170 & 32138 & -30274 & 18205 \\ 23170 & -32138 & 30274 & -27246 & 23170 & -18205 & 12540 & -6393 \end{bmatrix}$$

Each element in the first row of the input matrix X is multiplied by each element in the first column of matrix C^t and added together to get the first value Z_{00} of the intermediate matrix Z. To get Z_{01} , each element of row zero in X is multiplied by each element in the first column of C^t and added and so on.

$$\begin{aligned} Z_{(0,0)} &= 23170 (x_{00} + x_{01} + x_{02} + x_{03} + x_{04} + x_{05} + x_{06} + x_{07}) \\ Z_{(0,1)} &= 32138x_{00} + 27246x_{01} + 18205x_{02} + 6393x_{03} - 6393x_{04} - 18205x_{05} - 27246x_{06} - 32138x_{07} \\ &= 32138(x_{00} - x_{07}) + 27246(x_{01} - x_{06}) + 18205(x_{02} - x_{05}) + 6393(x_{03} - x_{04}) \\ Z_{(0,2)} &= 30274(x_{00} + x_{07}) + 12540(x_{01} + x_{06}) - 12540(x_{02} + x_{05}) - 30274(x_{03} + x_{04}) \\ Z_{(0,3)} &= 27246(x_{00} - x_{07}) - 6393(x_{01} - x_{06}) - 32138(x_{02} - x_{05}) - 18205(x_{03} - x_{04}) \\ Z_{(0,4)} &= 23170(x_{00} + x_{07}) - 23170(x_{01} + x_{06}) - 23170(x_{02} + x_{05}) + 23170(x_{03} + x_{04}) \\ Z_{(0,5)} &= 18205(x_{00} - x_{07}) - 32138(x_{01} - x_{06}) + 6393(x_{02} - x_{05}) + 27246(x_{03} - x_{04}) \\ Z_{(0,6)} &= 12540(x_{00} + x_{07}) - 30274(x_{01} + x_{06}) + 30274(x_{02} + x_{05}) - 12540(x_{03} + x_{04}) \\ Z_{(0,7)} &= 6393(x_{00} - x_{07}) - 18205(x_{01} - x_{06}) + 27246(x_{02} - x_{05}) - 32138(x_{03} - x_{04}) \\ \text{Or:} \\ Z_{(k,0)} &= 23170 (x_{k0} + x_{k1} + x_{k2} + x_{k3} + x_{k4} + x_{k5} + x_{k6} + x_{k7}) \\ Z_{(k,1)} &= 32138(x_{k0} - x_{k7}) + 27246(x_{k1} - x_{k6}) + 18205(x_{k2} - x_{k5}) + 6393(x_{k3} - x_{k4}) \\ Z_{(k,2)} &= 30274(x_{k0} + x_{k7}) + 12540(x_{k1} + x_{k6}) - 12540(x_{k2} + x_{k5}) - 30274(x_{k3} + x_{k4}) \\ Z_{(k,3)} &= 27246(x_{k0} - x_{k7}) - 6393(x_{k1} - x_{k6}) - 32138(x_{k2} - x_{k5}) - 18205(x_{k3} - x_{k4}) \\ Z_{(k,4)} &= 23170(x_{k0} + x_{k7}) - 23170(x_{k1} + x_{k6}) - 23170(x_{k2} + x_{k5}) + 23170(x_{k3} + x_{k4}) \\ Z_{(k,5)} &= 18205(x_{k0} - x_{k7}) - 32138(x_{k1} - x_{k6}) + 6393(x_{k2} - x_{k5}) + 27246(x_{k3} - x_{k4}) \\ Z_{(k,6)} &= 12540(x_{k0} + x_{k7}) - 30274(x_{k1} + x_{k6}) + 30274(x_{k2} + x_{k5}) - 12540(x_{k3} + x_{k4}) \\ Z_{(k,7)} &= 6393(x_{k0} - x_{k7}) - 18205(x_{k1} - x_{k6}) + 27246(x_{k2} - x_{k5}) - 32138(x_{k3} - x_{k4}) \\ \text{where } k &= 0, 2, \dots, 7. \end{aligned}$$

As shown, input X_{00} gets multiplied by all the coefficients in the first row of C^t , and input X_{01} gets multiplied by all the coefficients in the second row of C^t , and so on. The calculation is implemented by using eight multipliers and storing the coefficients in ROMs. At the first clock, the eight inputs x_{00} to x_{07} are multiplied by the eight values in column one, resulting in eight products (P_{00_0} to P_{00_7}). At the eighth clock, the eight inputs are multiplied by the eight values in column eight resulting in eight products (P_{07_0} to P_{07_7}). From the equations for Z , the intermediate values for the first row of Z are computed:

$$Z_{00} = P_{00_0} + P_{00_1} + P_{00_2} + P_{00_3} + P_{00_4} + P_{00_5} + P_{00_6} + P_{00_7}$$

$$Z_{01} = P_{01_0} + P_{01_1} + P_{01_2} + P_{01_3} + P_{01_4} + P_{01_5} + P_{01_6} + P_{01_7}$$

$$Z_{ij} = P_{ij_0} + P_{ij_1} + P_{ij_2} + P_{ij_3} + P_{ij_4} + P_{ij_5} + P_{ij_6} + P_{ij_7}$$

Where $i = 0$ to 7 , the matrix X row number and $j = 0$ to 7 , the matrix C^t column number. The intermediate values for the second row of Z , Z_{1K} , are computed by using P_{1K} values. The 8×8 Z matrix can be calculated using these equations. The values for Z_0 ($0-7$) can be calculated in eight clock cycles. (If the adder output is also registered, Z_{07} is calculated at the ninth clock cycle). All 64 values of Z are calculated in 64 clock cycles and then the process is repeated. The values of Z correspond to the 1D-DCT of the input X . Once the Z values are calculated, the 2D-DCT function Y can be calculated from $Y = CZ$.

Fig 3.2.1: Block Diagram of 1D - DCT

$$C = \begin{bmatrix} 23170 & 23170 & 23170 & 23170 & 23170 & 23170 & 23170 & 23170 \\ 32138 & 27246 & 18205 & 6393 & -6393 & -18205 & -27246 & -32138 \\ 30274 & 12540 & -12540 & -30274 & -30274 & -12540 & 12540 & 30274 \\ 27246 & -6393 & -32138 & -18205 & 18205 & 32138 & 6393 & -27246 \\ 23170 & -23170 & -23170 & 23170 & 23170 & -23170 & -23170 & 23170 \\ 18205 & -32138 & 6393 & 27246 & -27246 & -6393 & 32138 & -18205 \\ 12540 & -30274 & 30274 & -12540 & -12540 & 30274 & -30274 & 12540 \\ 6393 & -18205 & 27246 & -32138 & 32138 & -27246 & 18205 & -6393 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$Z = \begin{bmatrix} z00 & z01 & z02 & z03 & z04 & z05 & z06 & z07 \\ z10 & z11 & z12 & z13 & z14 & z15 & z16 & z17 \\ z20 & z21 & z22 & z23 & z24 & z25 & z26 & z27 \\ z30 & z31 & z32 & z33 & z34 & z35 & z36 & z37 \\ z40 & z41 & z42 & z43 & z44 & z45 & z46 & z47 \\ z50 & z51 & z52 & z53 & z54 & z55 & z56 & z57 \\ z60 & z61 & z62 & z63 & z64 & z65 & z66 & z67 \\ z70 & z71 & z72 & z73 & z74 & z75 & z76 & z77 \end{bmatrix}$$

Each element in the first row in the coefficient matrix C is multiplied by each element in the first column of matrix Z and added together to get the first value Y00 of the output matrix Y. To get Y01, each element of row zero in C is multiplied by each element in the first column of Z and is added as before. Multiplying row k of C by column zero of Z results in the coefficient YK0. All the elements in the first row of matrix Z are multiplied by all the elements in the first column of matrix C.

$$\begin{array}{l} 23170 \rightarrow \\ 23170 \rightarrow \end{array} \begin{bmatrix} z00 & z01 & z02 & z03 & z04 & z05 & z06 & z07 \\ z10 & z11 & z12 & z13 & z14 & z15 & z16 & z17 \\ z20 & z21 & z22 & z23 & z24 & z25 & z26 & z27 \\ z30 & z31 & z32 & z33 & z34 & z35 & z36 & z37 \\ z40 & z41 & z42 & z43 & z44 & z45 & z46 & z47 \\ z50 & z51 & z52 & z53 & z54 & z55 & z56 & z57 \\ z60 & z61 & z62 & z63 & z64 & z65 & z66 & z67 \\ z70 & z71 & z72 & z73 & z74 & z75 & z76 & z77 \end{bmatrix}$$

The calculation is implemented by using eight multipliers and storing the coefficients in ROMs. At the first clock, the eight coefficients in row zero of C are multiplied by the eight values in the first column of Z and are added together to result in Y00. At the eighth clock, the eight values of row zero of C are multiplied by the eight values in column eight of Z. The resultant is added to give Y07.

Fig 3.2.2: Block Diagram of 2D - DCT

Fig 3.2.3: RTL Schematic of 2-DCT Module

XIN (7:0) : This is 8 bit input to the DCT Module which is derived from the image block, 64 pixel values are given as input to the dct module as it works on 8X8 block size each time.

CLK: This signal acts as a clock to the DCT Module.

RST: This is act as reset to the DCT Module.

Dct_2d (11:0): This is 12 bit output of the DCT Module from where the transformed coefficient of the input image pixel values is retrieved.

rdy_out: This pin indicates start of data bits at dct_2d (11:0) pin, it becomes high at the 94th clk pulse after which the data is continuously sent at the outputs for the next 64 clk pulses.

3.3 IMPLEMENTATION STRATEGY

3.3.1 Description:

As shown in the above diagram, first the image is taken from source (memory) then using MATLAB it is converted into a matrix form (which is useful for digital processing) then on that image successively compression is done. Then from the simulation results digits are extracted which are placed back in matrix for and stored in memory location 1.

In second step a source image is given to MATLAB so that it will result into a matrix form for that image and that result is stored at memory location2.

Then two images are compare which are stored at memory location 1 and location2 and then the results are compared.

3.3.2 Applications

DCT is a typical building block for image processing, printers, desktop video editing, digital still cameras, surveillance systems, and video conferencing cores.

Features

- DCT supported on an 8x8 block of samples.
- DCT operations performed at one clock per sample.
- DCT input precision 8 bits; output precision 12 bits.

- High clock speed and low gate count achieved.
- Suitable for JPEG designs.
- Fully Synchronous design.
- Available as fully functional and synthesizable VHDL core
- Conclude for the best, efficient and low power family.

3.3.3 Test Procedure

- 1) The Input to the test bench waveform is the values obtained from the Image Matrix of the Matlab.
- 2) The DCT Coefficients thus obtained are to be verified whether they are correct or not.
- 3) The DCT coefficients obtained from ModelSim software are used to make a DCT Matrix in Matlab.

Commands to generate cosine matrix in Matlab.

```
function [c]=dct_mtx(n);

{% this funtion is used to generate the cosine matrix of size nXn}.

out1=dctmtx(n);

c=65535*out1;

return;
```

3.4 DESIGN STRATEGY

Summary: This document describes the step-by-step process to create, simulate, and implement a Xilinx FPGA-based design.

Required Software: (versions as of 8 March 2005)

1. Xilinx ISE WebPACK version 7.1
2. Model Technology ModelSim XE-II Starter version 5.8

Step 1 of 7 — Create your conceptual design:

1. Draw the I/O block diagram of your overall circuit, i.e., draw a rectangle with input pins on the left side and output pins on the right side, and write a name for each signal pin.

2. Draw the high-level (register-level) diagram of your design. This diagram will help you visualize the hardware when you write your circuit descriptions.
3. Determine assertion levels (active levels) of your I/O signals by planning what type of external circuit devices will connect to your FPGA.

Step 2 of 7 — Create the template VHDL files:

1. Start VHDL Template Maker (VTM).
2. Enter the number of input and output ports. Bit vectors (busses) count as a single port. Next, enter the information specific to your design (module name, port names, port widths, and descriptive comments). Standard prefixes can be added to the beginning of each identifiers. These prefixes make it easier to interpret your signal names, and also keep related identifiers together when displayed in a simulation tool.
3. Select “Make Circuit” to create the synthesizable circuit template. Copy the text into a file called circuitname.Vhd, replacing circuit name with a descriptive label for your module.
4. Select “Make Test bench” to create the test bench template. Copy the text into a file called circuit name Tb.Vhd.

Step 3 of 7 — Enter your VHDL descriptions:

You may use the text editor of your choice to enter your synthesizable circuit and testbench descriptions. The following steps assume that you will soon proceed to simulation, so the ModelSim editor is used. The ModelSim editor uses VHDL syntax color-coding which helps you to write a correct description.

1. Launch ModelSim, and select “File — New — Project”
2. Enter values into the “Project Name” and “Project Location” fields. Keep the default work for “Default Library Name.” Click “OK” when finished.
3. Double-click the “Add Existing File” icon, and navigate to the VHDL template files you created in Step 2. You can select multiple files (use Shift+Click and Ctrl+Click), or enter them one at a time. Be sure to add files as type “VHDL,” then click the “Next” button.

4. Identify the “Workspace” panel on the left side of the ModelSim main window, and double click a .Vhd file to open it in the editor. Add your circuit description to complete the template file. Repeat for the remaining .Vhd files.

NOTE: VTM assumes all outputs in the synthesizable circuit will be created from a procedural assignment (always block), so the outputs are automatically declared as register identifiers. If you choose to use a continuous assignment instead (assign statement), simply delete or comment out the associated register declaration.

5. Use Ctrl+S to save each file.

Step 4 of 7 — Perform functional verification (simulation):

1. Create a simulation macro file (known as a “do” file): Go to the ModelSim main window, and select “File — New — Source — Other”, and enter the content of the “do” file. For example:

```
# Example "do" file (a '#' character is a comment)
#
# List each .Vhd file in your project to be compiled
vlog demo.Vhd demo_tb.Vhd
# List the module name of your testbench (not the filename!)
vsim Demo_TESTBENCH
# Open the waveform viewer window, and look at all the input
# and output signals (*' is wildcard character)
view wave
add wave *
# Open the structure viewer and signal names viewer windows
view structure
view signals
# Run the simulation for "a long time" or until $stop encountered
run 1000ns
```

2. Save the macro file using a name similar to “sim.do” and say “yes” when prompted about adding the file to the project.

NOTE: Type ”edit sim.do” at the ModelSim prompt in order to view or update the file contents later on.

3. Run the simulation by either double-clicking the “sim.do” line in the ModelSim workspace (you may need to select the “Project” tab at the lower left) or by typing “do sim.do” at the ModelSim prompt.

4. Iterate on your design as follows: edit the source file that needs attention (select the “Project” tab in the ModelSim workspace and double-click the .Vhd file), save the file (Ctrl+S), and rerun the simulation (press the up-arrow at the ModelSim command prompt to retrieve the previous “do sim.do” command).

NOTE: The testbench source file will be displayed when the simulation stops because the simulation pointer halts at the \$stop line; however, the file is displayed in read-only mode (refer to the status indicator at the bottom of the editor), thus it is necessary to open the file from within the “Projects” tab.

5. The waveform display may be customized:

- Right-click on the signal name in the waveform window. The “Radix” option can be used to select binary, decimal, hexadecimal, and other display modes for busses (bit vectors)
- Trace order can be adjusted by clicking and holding on a signal name and dragging it to a new location
- Additional signal traces at any level in the hierarchy can be added: select the module of interest from the “structure” window, select the desired signal(s) from the “signals” window, then right-click and select “Add to Wave.”
- Save the waveform display using “Save — Format” and save to the default “wave.do” file.
- Update the simulation macro file (“sim.do”) by replacing the “add wave *” line with “do wave.do” I strongly recommend that you do not proceed until

you are 100% confident that your design performs according to specifications! Debugging is much easier and faster in the simulator.

Step 5 of 7 — Synthesize your design to a bitstream file:

1. Start Xilinx ISE WebPACK, and create a new project by selecting “File — New Project...” (note that Xilinx will open the most recently-used project, so you want to begin from scratch here).

NOTE: It is possible to write a VHDL description that simulates successfully in Step 4, and yet is incompatible in some way with the hardware synthesis or implementation steps in Xilinx ISE. This is not necessarily a shortcoming of ISE, but rather is due to the fact that VHDL is inherently a simulation and modeling language, and hardware synthesis tools only deal with a subset of the language. The bottom line: you need to learn how to write synthesizable descriptions.

2. Select a single word for the name of your project, and select the directory for your project files. Ensure that “HDL” is selected for the top-level module, and click “Next”.
3. Enter the following information (touch the right side of the white field to enable the pulldown menu):

Device Family = Spartan 3E

- Device = xc2s400
- Package = pq208
- Speed Grade = -5
- Top-Level Module Type = HDL
- Synthesis Tool = XST
- Simulator = ModelSim
- Generated Simulation Language = VHDL

Click the “Next” button two times.

4. Click the “Add Source” button and navigate to the subdirectory that contains your .Vhd files (you can select multiple files). You may be prompted to identify the source type; if so, select “VHDL Design File” for a synthesizable module, and

“VHDL Test Fixture File” for a testbench. Look carefully at the prompt in the pop-up window to determine for which file you are choosing the type.

5. Uncheck the “Copy to Project” checkboxes if you prefer that the original files be used. This would be especially important if you are running ModelSim in stand-alone mode and you need both ISE WebPACK and ModelSim to work from a common set of files. Click “Next” then “Finish.”
6. Single-click your top-level module in the “Sources” window in the upper left corner. Identify the “Processes” window in the lower left corner, and expand the “User Constraints” hierarchy button by clicking the plus sign. Double-click the “Edit Constraints” process, and say “Yes” to the next prompt.

IMPORTANT: You must select the top-level module first before you edit the constraints, because it is possible to associate a UCF with submodules.

7. Use the “UCF Generators for Xilinx Boards” to create the user constraints file, or UCF (refer to the “Required Software” section at the beginning of this document for details). The UCF generator is an Excel spreadsheet that translates your VHDL port names into pin assignments. Instructions for using the spreadsheet are included at the top of the spreadsheet. Copy the text from the yellow box in the UCF generator to the editor in ISE WebPACK, then save the file in ISE.

NOTE: Consider saving the UCF generator to your own file so that updates and changes can easily be made later on.

8. Start the hardware synthesizer by first selecting your top-level module in the upper left “Sources” panel, then double-click the “Synthesize” process on the lower left “Processes” panel.

NOTE 1: A green checkmark on a process means all is well; a yellow exclamation point means one or more warnings were generated, and a red X means a fatal error. You can find the error messages in the scrolling window at the bottom of the Project Navigator, and in some cases you can also find the error messages in the report file associated with each process in the lower left “Processes” window (you need to expand the hierarchy to find the reports).

NOTE 2: Ignoring yellow warnings in synthesis will almost always lead to fatal errors in the implementation step, so find and correct the problem(s) now.

Always begin by attacking the first problem mentioned in the warning/error list, since many (or possibly all) of the subsequent messages may stem from the first problem.

NOTE 3: Once you have corrected a problem, rerun by right-clicking the “Synthesize” process and selecting “Rerun.”

NOTE 4: Expand the “Synthesize” process to find the synthesis report (includes the device utilization summary, so you can find out how much of the FPGA resources were used). The “RTL Schematic” viewer gives you a schematic view of the hardware that was synthesized from your VHDL description.

9. Start the implementation tools by double-clicking the “Implement Design” process on the lower left “Processes” panel. When finished, verify that your pinout is correct by expanding the “Implement Design” process and then the “Place & Route” process, then double-click “Pad Report.” Look for your VHDL port names in the second column, and the pin numbers in the first column.

IMPORTANT: If your UCF file does not exist, or is not associated properly with your top-level module, then you will end up with a random pin assignment. At best this will appear as very strange behavior on the evaluation board, and at worst will give the impression of a completely dead evaluation board! If you encounter totally unexpected behavior with your hardware, then check the pad report.

10. Right-click on the “Generate Programming File” process, select “Properties,” select the “Startup Options” tab, and specify the “JTAG Clock” option for the “FPGA Start-Up Clock” (you only need to do this step one time for a given project).
11. Create the bit stream file by double-clicking the “Generate Programming File” process.

NOTE: In general you can run all previous processes by double-clicking the desired final process. For example, if you make a change to the .Vhd file, the implementation data will be cleared (all the checkmarks vanish), and double-clicking the “Generate Programming File” process will cause the synthesis and implementation processes to run automatically. If you need to re-generate all

project files from scratch, select the “Project” pull down menu at the top of the main window and choose “Cleanup Project Files.”

Step 6 of 7 — Download the bit stream file to the FPGA:

1. Ensure that the Xilinx 3E board is powered (power LED will be on).
2. Ensure that the parallel-port connector is connected to your PC. Take special care that the other end of the cable is properly plugged onto the JTAG header (match the signal names).
3. Ensure that the switch SW1 on the Xilinx 3E board (a slider switch next to the JTAG header) is set to “JTAG.” Set this back to the “PORT” position after downloading if your design needs to use the parallel port connector.
4. Expand the “Generate Programming File” process and double-click “Configure Device (iMPACT)”.
5. Click the “Next” button two times, say “OK,” choose your .bit file, and say “OK” again.
6. Right-click the FPGA icon in the iMPACT main window and select “Program...”
7. Ensure that the “Verify” option is not checked, and click “OK.” You will see a download progress indicator, and then success (or failure) will be displayed. If power is removed from the Xilinx board, you will need to download your bitstream file again, since the FPGA is an SRAM-based device.
8. When you make any changes that necessitate the production of a new bit file, do not double-click the “Configure Device (iMPACT)” process to re-run all the upstream processes, but instead double-click the “Generate Programming File” process. Once the new bitstream file is ready, simply switch to the iMPACT application that is already running, unless you had closed it earlier.

NOTE: Avoid launching more than one iMPACT application, since only one of them will be able to establish communications with the Xilinx board.

IMPORTANT: Right-click the FPGA icon in the iMPACT main window, select “Assign New Configuration File...” and specify your .bit file again. iMPACT does not rescan the new .bit file until you do this step. If you forget, you will be left

with the impression that your change to the source file has apparently had no effect.

Step 7 of 7 — Test your design:

1. Try varying the input devices and watching the output devices. If everything works OK, then celebrate!
2. If the board seems dead, or acts very strangely, it is possible that your pin assignments are missing or otherwise incorrect. If you do not have a UCF file, then the implementation tools will make a random pin assignment.
3. Consider making a simple file (such as an inverter connected between a switch and an LED) that can be used as a sanity check on your board.

Additional tips:

1. You can edit your VHDL files in the Xilinx ISE environment. Double-click the .Vhd file in the “Sources” panel to open it in the editor.
2. If you need to change the target device once you have implemented the project (e.g., take your design from a Spartan family device to a Virtex device), right-click on the target device line in the “Sources” panel, select “Properties,” enter your new information, and then reimplement your design by double-clicking the “Implement” process.
3. You can remove files from your project by selecting the desired file from the “Sources” panel, right-clicking, and choosing “Remove.” Note that your file does not get deleted from the file system, but simply becomes unknown to the Xilinx Project Navigator.
4. If something seems “not quite right” about the behavior of the software tool, try selecting “Project — Cleanup Project Files” to start from the beginning.
5. You can learn the resource usage of your design such as slice count and IO block count by opening the “Map Report” located in the process “Implement Design — Map — Map Report.”
6. You can see a schematic representation of the hardware version of your VHDL description by looking at the “RTL Schematic” viewer under the “Synthesize” process.

7. You can see how your design was routed on the chip itself by looking under “Implement Design — Place & Route — View/Edit Placed Design.” Just look, don’t actually change the design!
8. After this you can realize your design using actual design with proper timing and space constraints defined for the implementation.

3.5 PCB LAYOUTS

Fig 3.6.1: Bottom view

Fig 3.6.2: Component layout

Fig 3.6.3: Top view

CHAPTER 4

RESULTS, DISCUSSION AND FUTURE WORK

4.1 INPUT

A1.BMP IMAGE MATRIX

15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15
15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15
15	15	0	0	0	0	15	15
15	15	0	0	0	0	15	15
15	15	0	0	0	0	15	15
15	15	0	0	0	0	15	15
15	15	15	15	0	0	15	15
15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15

4.2 OUTPUT DERIVED FROM MATLAB

DCT MATRIX A1.BMP

87	2	32	-4	0	3	-13	0
5	-2	-4	5	0	-3	2	0
27	1	-24	-2	0	2	10	0
-1	1	1	-1	0	1	0	0
4	-2	-4	4	0	-3	1	0
-5	3	5	-6	0	4	-2	0
-7	-3	6	6	0	-4	-2	0
-3	2	3	-3	0	2	-1	0

4.3 RESULTS OBTAINED THROUGH VHDL IN MODELSIM

DISCUSSION

The core FPGA design had impressive results as described throughout the system overview sections. In simulation on the FPGA, assuming we had streaming inputs and outputs, the dct core takes 64 clock cycles for the first block, and as long as the data stream is constant, it will take an additional 29 clock cycles. As this core design is fully synchronous, it should give the same result in implementation.

The output is obtained from the 94th clock pulse and successively continues for next 64 clock pulses. For the whole image we need to first divide it into a finite number of blocks of 8*8 samples each and then operate upon each block individually, and then finally merge them at the output to get the transformed image.

Interleaving Image Components: Currently, the way this implementation runs is to encode the image components sequentially. This can potentially lower the time required to encode a color image.

Motion JPEG is arguably the most interesting application to this project. Simulation results show that the throughput of the DCT core is fast enough to achieve motion JPEG required speeds. This project would likely require a daughter circuit board to mate to the I/O of the FPGA pinned out on the card. This daughter board would likely have a camera, and memory, which could allow for multiple data paths in sending data to the encoder, and retrieving data to store into memory.

FUTURE WORK

In the process of developing this project, there were several ideas that were never integrated into the design. As this is the JPEG baseline algorithm, there are many extensions. The building blocks used in this design can be utilized in the JPEG extensions, as well as other compression algorithms. Also, there are many optimizations which can be performed on this design to improve throughput. The whole system integration on a single chip along with interfacing of various components such as controllers ,RAM, RTC and other peripheral chips will allow us to build and develop new and advanced systems for applications such as machine vision and video transmission through internet and other multimedia applications efficiently. The code can be further optimized by instantiating embedded adders and multipliers when targeting the Virtex™-II series of FPGAs. After an initial latency of 92 clock cycles, one 2D-DCT value is output at every clock.

4.4 HDL SYNTHESIS REPORT

Macro Statistics		4-bit adder	: 1
# Multipliers	: 8	7-bit adder	: 1
11x7-bit multiplier	: 4	8-bit adder	: 4
8x7-bit multiplier	: 4	9-bit adder	: 4
		9-bit subtractor	: 4
# Adders/Subtractors	: 41		
11-bit adder	: 5	# Counters	: 4
12-bit adder	: 1	32-bit up counter	: 1
12-bit addsub	: 4	4-bit up counter	: 1
19-bit adder	: 7	7-bit up counter	: 2
2-bit subtractor	: 1		
20-bit adder	: 7	# Registers	: 153
3-bit adder	: 2	1-bit register	: 19

10-bit register	: 4	Macro Statistics :	
11-bit register	: 77	# Registers	: 312
12-bit register	: 12	# 1-bit register	: 179
19-bit register	: 7	# 10-bit register	: 4
2-bit register	: 1	# 11-bit register	: 77
20-bit register	: 7	# 12-bit register	: 12
4-bit register	: 1	# 19-bit register	: 7
7-bit register	: 1	# 20-bit register	: 7
8-bit register	: 16	# 4-bit register	: 1
9-bit register	: 8	# 7-bit register	: 1
# Latches	: 2	# 8-bit register	: 16
1-bit latch	: 2	# 9-bit register	: 8
# Comparators	: 2	# Multiplexers	: 2
4-bit comparator less	: 1	# 11-bit 4-to-1 multiplexer:	1
7-bit comparator less	: 1	# 11-bit 64-to-1 multiplexe:	1
# Multiplexers	: 2	# Adders/Subtractors	: 41
11-bit 4-to-1 multiplexer	: 1	# 11-bit adder	: 5
11-bit 64-to-1 multiplexer	: 1	# 12-bit adder	: 1
# Xors	: 8	# 12-bit addsub	: 4
1-bit xor2	: 8	# 19-bit adder	: 7
		# 20-bit adder	: 7
Design Statistics		# 32-bit adder	: 4
# IOs	: 23	# 7-bit adder	: 1
		# 8-bit adder	: 4

# 9-bit adder	: 4	# LUT4	: 39
# 9-bit subtractor	: 4	# LUT4_D	: 17
		# LUT4_L	: 52
# Multipliers	: 8	# MUXCY	: 445
# 11x7-bit multiplier	: 4	# MUXF5	: 176
# 8x7-bit multiplier	: 4	# MUXF6	: 88
		# MUXF7	: 44
# Comparators	: 2	# MUXF8	: 22
# 4-bit comparator less	: 1	# VCC	: 1
# 7-bit comparator less	: 1	# XORCY	: 441
		# FlipFlops/Latches	: 1561
Cell Usage :		# FDC	: 435
# BELS	: 2556	# FDCE	: 1063
# BUF	: 3	# FDP	: 8
# GND	: 1	# FDPE	: 42
# INV	: 164	# FDR	: 11
# LUT1	: 53	# LDC	: 2
# LUT1_L	: 39	# Clock Buffers	: 1
# LUT2	: 275	# BUFGP	: 1
# LUT2_D	: 5	# IO Buffers	: 22
# LUT2_L	: 47	# IBUF	: 9
# LUT3	: 225	# OBUF	: 13
# LUT3_D	: 2	# MULTs	: 8
# LUT3_L	: 417	# MULT18X18	: 8

Device utilization summary:

Selected Device: 3s400pq208-5

Number of Slices:	1256	out of	3584	35%
Number of Slice Flip Flops:	1561	out of	7168	21%
Number of 4 input LUTs:	1171	out of	7168	16%
Number of bonded IOBs:	23	out of	141	16%
Number of MULT18X18s:	8	out of	16	50%
Number of GCLKs:	1	out of	8	12%

Timing Summary:

Speed Grade: -5

Minimum period: 8.770ns (Maximum Frequency: 114.022MHz)

Minimum input arrival time before clock: 1.572ns

Maximum output required time after clock: 10.911ns

Maximum combinational path delay: No path found

CHAPTER 5

CONCLUSION

The DCT, the one we are implementing here is lossy compression technique. An image reconstructed following lossy compression contains degradation relative to the original. Often this is because the compression scheme completely discards redundant information. However, lossy schemes are capable of achieving much higher compression. Under normal viewing conditions, no visible loss is perceived (visually lossless). The Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT) is a technique that converts a spatial domain waveform into its constituent frequency components as represented by a set of coefficients. One-dimensional DCT has most often been used in two dimensional DCT, by employing the row-column decomposition, which is also more suitable for hardware implementation. Typically the DCT coefficients produced have most of the block's energy in a few frequency domain elements, and hence quantization and coding is applied after DCT to provide the actual compression.

This core can perform the two dimensional Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT) on an 8x8 block of samples. It is simple and fully synchronous design which allows for fast operation while maintaining a low gate count. It also offers high performance and many features to meet your multimedia, digital video and digital printing applications. This module also includes the ability to parameterize the DCT function and to guarantee performance.

CHAPTER 6

APPENDIX

REFERENCE DESIGN NO: - 1

QUANTIZATION

Summary: This application note describes a reference design to do a quantization and inverse quantization of MPEG-2 video signals. After a brief introduction, the process of using JPEG and MPEG-2 standards for quantizing matrices is developed. Finally, implementing the Xilinx solution for quantization is described.

Introduction to Quantization

Quantization is the process of selectively discarding visual information without a significant loss in the visual effect. Quantization reduces the number of bits needed to store an integer value by reducing the precision of the integer. Each discrete cosine transform (DCT) component is divided by a separate quantization coefficient, and rounded to the nearest integer. The larger the quantization coefficient (i.e., coefficient weighting), the smaller the resulting answer and associated bits needed to express the DCT component. In the reverse process, the fractional bits are "rounded" and are recovered as zeros, constituting a precision loss from the original number. Quantization could be considered as input data binning where the number of bins is less than the number of possible input values. The number of bins is decided by the quantization factor Q . If the input data range is from one to 60, and if Q is 5, then $60/5$ is 12 bins (0 to 5, 6 to 10, and so on). A different input data range of 60 is now reduced to 12 possible bins. A DCT applied to an 8 x 8 block of pixel components has the effect of organizing the components into different spatial frequencies. The lower spatial frequency values or smoother spatial contours appear toward the upper left-hand corner of the coefficient matrix, and the higher spatial frequency values appear in the bottom right-hand corner. The uppermost left handed value is known as the DC component and expresses a solid color value for the entire block. If the entire block is a solid color, then only this value is needed to recreate the 8 x 8 pixel components. The human visual system is less sensitive to higher frequency spatial contours. Objects in a scene are recognized by lower frequency spatial contours. Quantization or reduction in the accuracy of the higher spatial frequency contour values does not

dramatically affect the image quality, since lower spatial frequencies are unchanged. The MPEG-2 standard uses different types of quantization. Quantization where parts of the higher frequency coefficients are not transmitted is considered zonal sampling. Scalar Quantization (SQ) is when quantization is performed on each individual coefficient. Quantization can also be performed on a group of coefficients together. This is known as Vector Quantization (VQ). Both uniform and non-uniform quantizers can be used depending on the problem. In some quantization, there is an increased threshold level around zero, described as a dead-zone. The effect of the increased threshold is to increase the number of coefficients quantized to zero. Small variations in input signals around zero are usually caused by noise. Quantization with a dead-zone around zero actually eliminates the noise around zero and improves the signal quality.

Why Use Quantization?

Quantization is done to achieve better compression. Quantization reduces the number of bits needed to store information by reducing the size of the integers representing the information in the scene. These are details that the human visual system ignores. This step represents one key segment in the multi- compression process. A reduction in the number of bits reduces storage capacity needed, improves bandwidth, and lowers implementation costs.

How to Use Quantization

JPEG

JPEG uses an 8 x 8 quantization matrix, the Q matrix, for each 8 x 8 DCT block to be compressed. For an 8-bit DCT coefficient, each element in the Q matrix can have an integer value between one and 255. The Q matrix for JPEG is designed using two techniques, a Q matrix developed using psycho visual experiments, and a Q matrix based on rate distortion theory and bit rate control. The default Q matrix is derived from the psycho visual experiments for luminance and chrominance components.

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \begin{array}{l}
 Q \text{ Table For Luminance} \\
 \begin{bmatrix}
 16 & 11 & 10 & 16 & 24 & 40 & 51 & 61 \\
 12 & 12 & 14 & 19 & 26 & 58 & 60 & 55 \\
 14 & 13 & 16 & 24 & 40 & 57 & 69 & 56 \\
 14 & 17 & 22 & 29 & 51 & 87 & 80 & 62 \\
 18 & 22 & 37 & 56 & 68 & 109 & 103 & 77 \\
 24 & 35 & 55 & 64 & 81 & 104 & 113 & 92 \\
 49 & 64 & 78 & 87 & 103 & 121 & 120 & 101 \\
 72 & 92 & 95 & 98 & 112 & 100 & 103 & 99
 \end{bmatrix}
 \end{array} \\
 \\
 \begin{array}{l}
 Q \text{ Table For Chrominance} \\
 \begin{bmatrix}
 17 & 18 & 24 & 47 & 99 & 99 & 99 & 99 \\
 18 & 21 & 26 & 66 & 99 & 99 & 99 & 99 \\
 24 & 26 & 56 & 99 & 99 & 99 & 99 & 99 \\
 47 & 66 & 99 & 99 & 99 & 99 & 99 & 99 \\
 99 & 99 & 99 & 99 & 99 & 99 & 99 & 99 \\
 99 & 99 & 99 & 99 & 99 & 99 & 99 & 99 \\
 99 & 99 & 99 & 99 & 99 & 99 & 99 & 99 \\
 99 & 99 & 99 & 99 & 99 & 99 & 99 & 99
 \end{bmatrix}
 \end{array}
 \end{array}$$

The quantization of DCT components in a JPEG picture is shown in Equation 1.

$$\text{Quantized Coefficient } (i,j) = \frac{DCT(i,j)}{Qmatrix(i,j)} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

MPEG-2

The MPEG standard consists of three different picture types. The intra-coded "I" picture where an "I" picture is coded with reference to itself (i.e., information from no other frames are used to code an "I" frame.) A predicted "P" picture is coded using information from a previous "P" or "I" picture. The information from a previous picture is used to predict the motion in time of the current P frame. A bidirectional "B" predicted frame uses information from past, and/or future "I" or "P" pictures. Motion compensated prediction is again used for coding B pictures. An intrapicture frame is quantized using the intra-quantizer matrix. The intra-frame AC coefficients (i.e., all coefficients other than (0,0)) are quantized without a dead-zone using an intra-quantizer matrix. The P (predictive) and B (bidirectional) frames are quantized by uniform quantizer with a dead-zone around zero. A dead zone is described as a quantized to zero area larger than the step size with decreasing sensitivity to input noise. A dead zone results in a string of zeroes at the output. A non-intra quantizer matrix is used in this application note. MPEG-2 also allows the use of a user specified quantization matrix.

The process of DCT coefficient quantization is described in this section. The output of a 2D-DCT is read out one value at a time as defined in the MPEG-2 standard. Each DCT coefficient is divided by a corresponding quantization matrix value supplied by

the quantization matrix. The encoder can use the default matrix or it can substitute a new user defined quantization matrix at a picture level and download it to the decoder via the bitstream.

In a 4:4:4 formats there is no decimation of chrominance components. For every one Y or luma component, there is one Cb and one Cr component. In 4:2:2 formats, both chrominance components are decimated by two horizontally, making the number of chrominance components along a given line be half the number of luminance components. In a 4:2:0 format, both chrominance components are decimated horizontally as well as vertically where the number of Cr or Cb components horizontally and vertically is half the number of luminance (Y) component. For every four Y samples, there is one Cr and one Cb sample.

With 4:2:0 data, two Q matrices are used, one for intra-macroblocks and one for non-intramacroblocks. For 4:2:2 and 4:4:4 data, four matrices are used, two sets (intra and non-intra) for luminance and two set's (intra and non-intra) for chrominance. The default matrices corresponding to the luminance portion are loaded first. For 4:2:2 and 4:4:4 data, a different user-defined chrominance matrix can be loaded later.

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \text{Intra Quantizer Matrix} \\
 \begin{bmatrix}
 8 & 16 & 19 & 22 & 26 & 27 & 29 & 34 \\
 16 & 16 & 22 & 24 & 27 & 29 & 34 & 37 \\
 19 & 22 & 26 & 27 & 29 & 34 & 34 & 38 \\
 22 & 22 & 26 & 27 & 29 & 34 & 37 & 40 \\
 22 & 26 & 27 & 29 & 32 & 35 & 40 & 48 \\
 26 & 27 & 29 & 32 & 35 & 40 & 48 & 58 \\
 26 & 27 & 29 & 34 & 38 & 46 & 56 & 69 \\
 27 & 29 & 35 & 38 & 46 & 56 & 69 & 83
 \end{bmatrix} \\
 \\
 \text{Non Intra Quantizer Matrix} \\
 \begin{bmatrix}
 16 & 16 & 16 & 16 & 16 & 16 & 16 & 16 \\
 16 & 16 & 16 & 16 & 16 & 16 & 16 & 16 \\
 16 & 16 & 16 & 16 & 16 & 16 & 16 & 16 \\
 16 & 16 & 16 & 16 & 16 & 16 & 16 & 16 \\
 16 & 16 & 16 & 16 & 16 & 16 & 16 & 16 \\
 16 & 16 & 16 & 16 & 16 & 16 & 16 & 16 \\
 16 & 16 & 16 & 16 & 16 & 16 & 16 & 16 \\
 16 & 16 & 16 & 16 & 16 & 16 & 16 & 16
 \end{bmatrix}
 \end{array}$$

When a sequence header code in the video bitstream is decoded, all quantization matrices are reset to the default matrices. User defined matrices can be downloaded in the sequence header or the "quant matrix" extension. The Q matrix has 64, 8-bit unsigned values. Value zero is not used since division by zero is not applicable.

The quantizations of AC coefficients are given in Equation 2.

$$QDCT(i,j) = \frac{\left[\frac{32 \times DCT(i,j)}{Qmatrix(i,j) \times Quantizer\ Scale} + k \right]}{2} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

Where $k = 0$ for intra blocks

$k = \text{sign of DCT coefficient for non-intra blocks}$

1 if $DCT(i,j) > 0$

0 if $DCT(i,j) == 0$

-1 if $DCT(i,j) < 0$

Q matrix (i,j) is the (i,j)TH element of the corresponding quantizer matrix given. Quantized (i,j) is limited to the range $[-2048, 2047]$.

For DC coefficients of intra-coded blocks, the quantizer step-size is determined by the selected DCT precision. The quantization of DCT components in an MPEG-2 picture is shown in Equation 3.

$$\text{Quantized Coefficient (0,0)} = \frac{DCT(0,0)}{k} \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

Where k is a constant determined by the DCT precision selected: $k = 8$ for 8-bit precision, $k = 4$ for 9-bit precision, $k = 2$ for 10-bit precision, and $k = 1$ for 11-bit precision. MPEG-2 allows changing the quantization scale factor on a macroblock basis to promote achieving better compression ratios. Each value in the quantization matrix is pre-scaled when multiplied by a single integer value, known as the quantizer scale code. The quantizer scale code is a 5-bit unsigned integer in the one to 31 range. The encoder/decoder uses this value until another quantizer scale code is encountered either in a slice or a macroblock. The value zero is forbidden. Each of the 31 values of the quantizer scale code are mapped to two sets of integers, called "quantizer_scale", ranging from one to 112. The quantizer scale type is used to indicate if either the quantizer scale code or the quantizer_scale applies. The value of the quantizer scale code is modifiable on a macroblock basis, making it useful as a fine-tuning parameter for bit-rate control, since it is not economical to send an entirely new matrix on a macroblock basis. This operation forces as many of the DCT coefficients to zero, or

near zero, as possible within the boundaries of the prescribed bit-rate and video quality parameters.

quantizer_scale_code	quantizer_scale[q_scale_type]	
	q_scale_type = 0	q_scale_type = 1
0	(forbidden)	
1	2	1
2	4	2
3	6	3
4	8	4
5	10	5
6	12	6
7	14	7
8	16	8
9	18	10
10	20	12
11	22	14
12	24	16
13	26	18
14	28	20
15	30	22
16	32	24
17	34	28
18	36	32
19	38	36
20	40	40
21	42	44
22	44	48
23	46	52
24	48	56
25	50	64
26	52	72
27	54	80
28	56	88
29	58	96
30	60	104
31	62	112

Table a: Relationship Between quantizer_scale and quantizer_scale_code

Implementation in a Xilinx FPGA

QUANTIZATION

When implementing Quantization in a Xilinx FPGA, start with Equation 2. Rewriting Equation 2 gives Equation 5.

$$\text{Quantized Coefficient}(i,j) = \frac{16 \times \text{DCT}(i,j)}{Q_{\text{matrix}}(i,j) \times \text{quantiser scale}} + \frac{k}{2} \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

All the possible values for $16/\text{quantiser_scale}$ are stored in ROM q_scale_mem . With two possible quantizer scale types, and with each type having 32 possible quantizer scale codes, the quantizer scale can have up to 64 different values. Since the Q matrix coefficients are up to 8-bits wide, these coefficients can have up to 256 possible values. $1/Q_{\text{matrix}}$ values are calculated for all the 256 values and are stored in a second ROM, q_value_mem . The 64 values of the Q matrix, either default, user-defined intra, or user-defined non-intra, are stored in RAMs called def_q_mem , $q_value_new_intra$, and $q_value_new_non_intra$ respectively. Each of the 64 Qmatrix values are used to choose the corresponding $1/Q_{\text{matrix}}$ value from the q_value_mem .

The input DCT value is multiplied with the corresponding value from q_value_mem . The result is then multiplied with the output of q_scale_mem , selected by the input quantizer scale code. Figure 1 shows the quantizer implementation in the decoder.

Figure a: Quantizer Implementation in the Decoder

REFERENCE DESIGN NO: - 2

HUFFMAN CODING

Summary: Huffman coding is used to code values statistically according to their probability of occurrence. Short code words are assigned to highly probable values and long code words to less probable values. Huffman coding is used in MPEG-2 to further compress the bitstream. This application note describes how Huffman coding is done in MPEG-2 and its implementation.

Introduction: The output symbols from RLE are assigned binary code words depending on the statistics of the symbol. Frequently occurring symbols are assigned short code words whereas rarely occurring symbols are assigned long code words. The resulting code string can be uniquely decoded to get the original output of the run length encoder. The code assignment procedure developed by Huffman is used to get the optimum code word assignment for a set of input symbols.

The procedure for Huffman coding involves the pairing of symbols. The input symbols are written out in the order of decreasing probability. The symbol with the highest probability is written at the top, the least probability is written down last. The least two probabilities are then paired and added. A new probability list is then formed with one entry as the previously added pair. The least symbols in the new list are then paired. This process is continued till the list consists of only one probability value. The values "0" and "1" are arbitrarily assigned to each element in each of the lists. Figure 1 shows the following symbols listed with a probability of occurrence where: A is 30%, B is 25%, C is 20%, D is 15%, and E = 10%.

Figure b: Huffman Coding Procedure

Steps

1. Adding the two least probable symbols gives 25%. The new symbol is F
2. Adding the two least probable symbols gives 45%. The new symbol is G
3. Adding the two least probable symbols gives 55%. The new symbol is H
4. Write "0" and "1" on each branch of the summation arrows. These binary values are called branch binaries.
5. For each letter in each column, copy the binary numbers from the column on the right, starting from the right most column (i.e., in column three, G gets the value "1" from the G in column four.) For summation branches, append the binary from the right-hand side column to the left of each branch binary. For A and C in column three append "0" from H in column four to the left of the branch binaries. This makes A "00" and B "01".
6. Completing step 5 gives the binary values for each letter: A is "00", B is "01", C is "11", D is "100", and E is "101". The input with the highest probability is represented by a code word of length two, whereas the lowest probability is represented by a code word of length three.

Huffman Coding in MPEG-2

MPEG is a non-adaptive coding system, the code table does not change with the input video sequence. Many image sequences were coded and the statistics used to define the entries in the MPEG-2 Huffman table. JPEG still image compression, using adaptive entropy coding, where the table entries can be modified to better suit a particular picture. JPEG also uses adaptive arithmetic coding where the code table is changeable depending on the change in the statistics of the JPEG image.

MPEG defines a set of variable-length code (VLC) for each of the probable run/level combinations. The run/level combinations not found in the table are represented by an escape code followed by a six-bit code for the run and an eight or 16-bit code for the level.

The end-of block

(EOB) code is used when all the remaining coefficients in the 8 x 8 block are zeroes. Coding of the 8 x 8 block starts from the DC coefficient in the zigzag order. When there are no more nonzero coefficients remaining in the zigzag order, the EOB code is used to terminate coding. Since the probability of occurrence of the EOB symbol is high, it is assigned a two bit code "10". The VLC tables used in MPEG-2 are not true Huffman codes. They are optimized for a range of bit rates to sample rate ratios. Most of the code words in the MPEG-2 tables were carried over from the H.261 standard. The DCT coefficient tables in MPEG-2 assume equal probability for both positive and negative coefficients. MPEG-2 VLC uses a new table, Table 8. It is better suited for the statistics of intra-coded blocks. The EOB code for Table 7 has two bits but for Table 8, the EOB has four bits. This implies that an intra-coded block can have on average of 24 or 16 non-zero AC coefficients. For non intra-coded blocks, the statistics point to an average of 22 or four non-zero AC coefficients. Both Table 7 and Table 8 have 113 entries. The VLC table consists of Huffman codes for different run/level combinations. The last bit "s" of the code denotes the sign of the level with $s = 0$ for positive and $s = 1$ for negative. The VLC table also includes the EOB code to indicate the status of the rest of the coefficients as zero. The EOB cannot occur as the only code in a block since no coding was done in the block. There are run/level combinations not defined in the VLC tables. When the variable length coder sees an undefined run/level combination, it codes the run into a 6-bit binary value and the level into a 12-bit signed level value. Before coding an undefined run/level pair, a 6-bit "escape code " is used to denote that the next six to 12 bits are not from the VLC table.

Encoding DC Coefficients

Due to high redundancy between adjacent quantized DC coefficients of 8 x 8 blocks, the difference in DC values is encoded using VLC. The difference signals range from -255 to 255 in MPEG-1 and from -2047 to 2047 in MPEG-2. The size of the differential DC value (`dct_dc_size`) is found in Table 1. The size denotes the number of bits used to represent a particular value (e.g., if the differential DC value is -78, the table shows a size seven. The seven bits will be used to represent the value -78. The `dct_dc_size` value is variable length coded using table Table 5 or Table 6. After

coding the size bits, -78 is represented as 111110,0110010 where the first six bits define the `dct_dc_size` and the next seven bits are used to code the value -78 . Two different VLC codes are used for coding the `dct_dc_size` for luma and chroma. The difference path for 8×8 blocks within a macroblock is calculated in the order shown in Figure2.

Figure c: Calculation Order in Adjacent Macroblocks

Differential DC	Size	Additional Code
-2047 to -1024	11	00000000000 to 01111111111
-1023 to -512	10	0000000000 to 0111111111
-511 to -256	9	000000000 to 011111111
-255 to -128	8	00000000 to 01111111
-127 to -64	7	0000000 to 0111111
-63 to -32	6	000000 to 011111
-31 to -16	5	00000 to 01111
-15 to -8	4	0000 to 0111
-7 to -4	3	000 to 011
-3 to -2	2	00 to 01
-1	1	0
0	0	
1	1	1
2 to 3	2	10 to 11
4 to 7	3	100 to 111
8 to 15	4	1000 to 1111
16 to 31	5	10000 to 11111
32 to 63	6	100000 to 111111
64 to 127	7	1000000 to 1111111
128 to 255	8	10000000 to 11111111
256 to 511	9	100000000 to 111111111
512 to 1023	10	1000000000 to 1111111111
1024 to 2047	11	10000000000 to 11111111111

Table b: Differential DC Additional Codes

AC Coefficients

The Huffman tables used for coding AC coefficients are selected based on the macroblock type and `intra_vlc_format` value according to Table 2. For MPEG-1 coding, only Table 7 is used. For MPEG-2, Table 8 is used for intra-coded blocks and Table 7 for non-intra coded blocks. In Table 7, there are two Huffman codes for the run/level combination of 0/1. The code "1s" is used if the 0/1 pair represents the first coefficient or the DC coefficient in the block. For subsequent 0/1 run/level pairs, "11s" is used as the Huffman code. The "s" in the code denotes the sign of the coefficient, "0" for positive and "1" for negative. The run/level pair for DC coefficient of "+1" and the EOB code has the same Huffman code. The differentiation is apparent since the EOB code will not be the first code in the block. In intra coding, since the DC value is coded separately, the first coded symbol is the first AC value. In this case, this first coded value can have a run/level of 0/1. A Huffman code of "11s" will not conflict with the EOB symbol. For a run/level pair that is not defined in the VLC Table 7 and Table 8, an escape code is used according to Table 9, followed by a 6-bit run symbol and 12-bit level symbol.

<code>intra_vlc_format</code>	0	1
intra coded blocks (<code>macroblock_intra = 1</code>)	Reference Table 7	Reference Table 8
non-intra coded blocks (<code>macroblock_intra = 0</code>)	Reference Table 7	Reference Table 7

Table c: Selection of DCT Coefficient VLC Tables

Notes:

This table was taken from ISO/IEC 13818-2: 1995 (E), Table 7-3.

Table 7 and Table 8 are stored in ROMs. The run/level value is used to access the ROM and the corresponding variable length code is read out.

Decoding DC Coefficient

Three predictor values are maintained for each color component. The predictor values are set at the start of the slice, or when a non-intra macroblock is decoded, or when a macroblock is skipped. The predictor values for different `intra_dc_precisions` are shown in Table 3.

intra_dc_precision	Bits of Precision	Reset Value
0	8	128
1	9	256
2	10	512
3	11	1024

Table d: Relationship Between intra_dc_precision and the Predictor Reset Value

Notes:

This table was taken from ISO/IEC 13818-2: 1995 (E), Table 7-2.(Reference Item 1)

The DC coefficient is decoded by first getting the differential value from the coded stream. This differential_dc value is then added to the predictor to get the actual DC value. The new predictor value then becomes the actual DC value just decoded. The decoding process can be described in the following manner (from ISO/IEC 13818-2: 1995 (E)(Reference Item 1)) QFS[0] shall be calculated from dc_dct_size and dc_dct_differential by any process equivalent to:

```

if ( dc_dct_size == 0 ) {
dct_diff = 0;
}
else
{
half_range = 2 ^ ( dc_dct_size - 1 );      ..... Note ^ denotes power (not XOR)
if ( dc_dct_differential >= half_range )
dct_diff = dc_dct_differential;
else
dct_diff = (dc_dct_differential + 1) - (2 * half_range);
}
QFS[0] = dc_dct_pred[cc] + dct_diff;
dc_dct_pred[cc] = QFS[0]

```

Note: `dct_diff` and `half_range` are temporary variables that are not used elsewhere in this specification. It is a requirement of the bitstream that `QFS[0]` shall lie in the range of zero to $2^8 + \text{intra dc precision} - 1$.

AC Coefficient

The run/level pair is decoded from the Huffman code using a look-up table (LUT). There are three possible options for the Huffman code. If the code represents an EOB, all the remaining coefficients are set to "0". If the code represents an escape code, the next six bits represent the run and the following 12 bits represent the level. If the VLC denotes a normal coefficient, then the run coefficients are set to zero and the following level coefficient is set to the level value depending on the value of `s`. When `s == 0`, the signed level is the same as level. When `s == 1`, the signed level is equal to $(-level)$.

Huffman Implementation

The run/length pair is mapped to variable length codes from the code table. The code words are concatenated together and the output is partitioned into fixed length segments. The implementation shown in figure 3 is similar to the one proposed by Lei and Sun (Reference Item 2).

Figure c: Huffman Implementation Block Diagram

REFERENCE DESIGN NO: - 3

VARIABLE LENGTH CODING

Summary: This application note describes the implementation of Variable Length Coding (VLC) on Xilinx devices. Zig-zag coding and run length coding are done in an MPEG-2 encoder. The zig-zag coding arranges the DCT coefficients in the order of increasing frequency. These coefficients are then coded as a run-length pair where run is the number of occurrences of a value and the length is the amplitude.

Introduction: Variable Length Coding (VLC) is the final lossless stage of the MPEG video compression unit. VLC is done to further compress the quantized image. VLC consists of three steps: zig-zag scanning, Run Length Encoding (RLE), and Huffman coding. At the decoder, VLC is the first step in the decoding process. Figure 1 shows VLC at the encoder.

Figure d: VLC at the Encoder

Zig-zag Scan: In zig-zag scanning the quantized coefficients are read out in a zig-zag order. By arranging the coefficients in this manner, RLE and Huffman coding can be done to further compress the data. The scan puts the high-frequency components together. These components are usually zeroes.

For MPEG-2 interlaced video, a top field and a bottom field consist of a frame frozen at different instances in time. If the frame has a moving object, the intra-coded blocks containing this moving object exhibit high vertical frequencies. These high frequencies are less likely to quantize to zero. In this case, implementing an alternate scan (alternate zig-zag scanning pattern) facilitates faster reception of the non-zero high frequencies. The alternate scan is an additional choice in the MPEG-2 standard. The MPEG-1 standard uses only the regular zig-zag scanning order. Figure 2 shows the zig-zag scan and the alternate scan.

ZigZag Scan Orders Allowed In MPEG-1 and MPEG-2

Alternate Scan Orders Allowed In MPEG-2 Only

Figure e: Zig-zag Scan Orders and Alternate Scan Orders (MPEG-2 Only)

Run Length Encoding (RLE)

Basics

The quantized coefficients are read out in a zig-zag order from DC component to the highest frequency component. RLE is used to code the string of data from the zig-zag scanner. Run length encoding codes the coefficients in the quantized block into a run length (or number of occurrences) and a level or amplitude. For example, transmit four coefficients of value "10" as: {10,10,10,10}. By using RLE, the level is 10 and the run of a value of 10 is four. By using RLE, {4,10} is transmitted, reducing the amount of data transmitted. Typically, RLE encodes a run of symbols into two bytes, a count and a symbol. By defining an 8 x 8 block without RLE, 64 coefficients are used. To further compress the data, many of the quantized coefficients in the 8 x 8 block are zero. Coding can be terminated when there are no more non-zero coefficients in the zig-zag sequence. Using the "end-of-block" code terminates the coding.

The compression ratio obtained by RLE is:

Compression Ratio = original size/compressed size: 1

Two examples of compression using RLE are described:

1. Consider the sequence --- aa0005555555zzzzaaaa

This string of characters can be compressed to form --- 2(a), 3(0), 7(5), 4(z), 4(a)

The 20-byte original string would only require 10 bytes of data to represent the string. In this case, RLE yields a compression ratio of 2 : 1.

2. Consider the string of numbers as follows --- 2, 0, 1, 2, 0, 1, 2, 0, 1

This string can be compressed to form --- 3 (2, 0, 1). Giving a compression ratio of = 9/4: 1, almost 2: 1.

RLE will not always result in compression. The amount of compression achieved depends on the data being compressed.

Consider the string --- 1, 2, f, 4, a, a,

After RLE gives --- 1(1),1(2),1(f),1(4),2(a).

To express the original string of 6 bytes, 10 bytes are used. Instead of compression, the original string has expanded. If each character in a string of 128 characters is different from the previous, each character will require 2 bytes to denote the run and level. In this case, 2 x 128 bytes are required to denote the original 128 bytes of information, with no compression available. RLE is most often used to compress black and white or 8-bit indexed color images where long runs are likely. RLE is not generally used for high color images. In photography, each pixel generally varies from the last. RLE cannot achieve high compression ratios compared to other compression methods, although it is easy to implement. Run length encoding is supported by most bitmap file formats (TIFF, BMP, and PCX). Long runs are rare in certain types of data (ASCII text files), and RLE is not a good compression choice. To encode a run in RLE, a minimum of two characters worth of information is required. A run of single character takes more space.

RLE Implementation

RLE in MPEG consists of denoting the "run of zeroes" followed by the value of the coefficient. Each AC coefficient is represented by the number of zeroes before the coefficient followed by the coefficient. RLE is very simple to implement. A flow chart of an RLE implementation is shown in Figure 3.

Figure f: Block Diagram of a Variable Length Coder Implementation

CHAPTER 7

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